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Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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TAIS Methodology and Guidelines

Deliverable D3.4

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Del. 3.4 TAIS methodology and guidelines [April, 2022]

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About RAISD	
Call (part) identifier	H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018
Topic	MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement
Fixed EC Keywords	Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

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RAISD Glossary

AB	Advisory Board
ALLEA	All European Academies
AR	Action Research
ARU	Action Research Unit
AUCL	All You Can Learn
CAS	Centri di Accoglienza Straordinaria (IT), Extraordinary Reception Centres
CASPa	Palermo Area CAS
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPP	Digitalised Personal Pathway
EC	European Commission
FDP	Forcibly Displaced People / Person/s
FRC	Finnish Red Cross
HE	Higher Education
HV	Highly Vulnerable
HVG	Highly Vulnerable Group
INMP	National Institute for Health, Migration and Poverty (Italy)
JSR	Jesuit Refugee Service
LGTBIQ	Lesbian, Gay, Transgender, Bisexual, Intersex and Queer or Questioning
LTE	Learning and Training Environment
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
MS	Milestone
NEET	People not in employment, education or training
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PRSF	Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum

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RAISD	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
RSS	Refugee Support System
SAI	System of Accommodation and Integration (Italy)
SEAD	Social, Emotional, Academic, Development
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Time-based
SEMs	Socio-Ecological Models
SO	Specific Objective
SSE	Social and Solidarity Economy
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
TAIS	Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
VC	Vulnerability Context
VG	Vulnerable Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The current deliverable D3.4 constitutes the final version of the report on TAIS methodology and guidelines, and it builds upon the previous D3.3 preliminary version. Whereas D3.3 offers the basic methodology guidance for the design and uptake of the Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) and covers partner organisations' insights on the process until the first evaluation round, the current deliverable engages in taking a deep look at the application of the methodology in the design, implementation and evaluation of the TAIS, pondering the benefits and challenges of the application of the triangular methodology consisting of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), Action Research (AR) and Socio-ecological models (SEMs). D4.3 offers guidelines for a correct use of the research approach and gives guidelines for integrating the methodology into the practice. A gender sensitive and integrated gender approach is one of the key principles of the RRI discipline that frames the project, and also, it is key for the TAIS process. Therefore, our team has considered it interesting to include step to step recommendations for embedding the gender approach into a research and innovation project, based on our experience with the project and the TAIS. First hand experiences can be useful for those interested in working in TAIS-related approaches in the future, and for this end, the current report also shares partner organisations insights about the methodological challenges and practical issues related to the daily practice of the TAIS. D3.4 mainly takes it from the second TAIS implementation round, describing the re-design and the practical changes that were required and implemented by the partners after the evaluation rounds, whereas the practical questions of the first implementation period are included in D3.3.

After the co-design of the TAIS by the multi-stakeholder teams of the Action Research Units (ARUs), the TAIS were implemented in 3 rounds, after each of which, an evaluation was carried out and adjustments made to the original designs. These successive iterations of action and evaluation are typical of the AR methodology used in the TAIS design and evaluation. They are particularly well-suited for the "tailored" nature of the strategies, as these are readjusted according to the forcible displaced persons' and other beneficiaries' needs and requirements that arise on the run and justify changes. Some examples of these during the pilots of the project have been incorporating new training contents, recruiting social workers to facilitate contact with the beneficiaries or moving action from face-to-face to online due to Covid-19 restrictions. AR provides a collaborative approach to research which became patent in the TAIS design and evaluation process, with the participation of diverse stakeholders, specially the Forcibly Displaced People (FDP) themselves and assisting civil society organisations.

This collaborative vision is also inherent in the RRI discipline that frames the project and suggests that all relevant stakeholders should be included in the co-design and -evaluation. The scope of this project research and innovation action, and thus, of the TAIS, is advocacy-focused, grounded in human rights, deeply gender-sensitive and seeks to obtain societally acceptable and sustainable results, aligned with the RRI principles.

The triangular methodology combines AR and RRI with the application of SEMs which permit to envision the interactions between social phenomena in three different interrelated and interdependent levels: micro/individual and family, meso/organisational and macro/policy making level. Evidently, the TAISs take place in the micro and meso levels, but still, the project has detected interesting insights for macro level recommendations in the frequent organisational and individual level activities, such as the training sessions, ARU meetings and evaluation sessions. Information about policy recommendations can be found in D9.9, more specific recommendations for a TAIS-

oriented approach in D3.5 and a discussion on ARUs as social laboratories for collaboration with stakeholders in D3.3, all available at RAISD website.

D3.4 offers a brief overview of the 8 TAIS pilots and describes the 3 methodological principles -RRI, AR and SEMs-, followed by the partners' description of the TAIS process after the first evaluation period, including practical aspects, benefits and difficulties inherent to the methodology triad. Thereafter, both expected and unexpected impacts caused by the TAIS are exposed and lessons learned as well as partner's ideas for TAIS future application are offered in final conclusions.

From a technical perspective, D3.4 is part of WP3 Methodological coordination, it is performed by task T3.3 Development of TAIS methodology and it responds to the Specific Objectives (SOs) SO5 Elaboration of recommendation to develop attention and inclusion strategies tailored to vulnerable groups and SO6 Validation of TAIS and their methodology through pilots. D3.4 is related to WP3 Milestones (MSs) MS4 Work methodology, MS10 First reviews of the working methodology and MS16 Catalogue of recommendations, which will be found in D3.5. The general RAISD methodology is explained in D3.2 Work methodology and guidelines that sets the norms and uses for the entire project, whereas more specific TAIS-related methodology framework and application guidelines are included in D3.3 and D.3.4.

The current deliverable D3.4 uses WP4 Vulnerability profiling report results (D4.2 Vulnerability context: definition and guidelines) as a base for the TAIS development and it is aligned with WP5 Design of tailored attention and inclusion strategies (D5.1 Catalogue of attention and inclusion strategies for FDP in the EU influence area and D5.3 TAIS: Definition and guidelines and D5.4 Catalogue of TAISs) and WP6 Action Research development (D6.1 Training and evaluation materials and D6.2 Report on implementation of TAIS in the ARUs). D3.4 follows the Ethics and quality requirements of WP1 (D2.2. Quality assurance plan and D3.1 Ethics plan). Evaluation mechanisms for TAISs and their results are established and detailed in WP7 Cross-analysis, in D7.2 Cross-pilot workshop reports and D7.4 Evaluation criteria: actor oriented and integrated evaluation.

The report plunges into the challenges and lessons learned from the 7 participating countries during the TAIS process, it describes the methodological triangulation and the potential benefits and difficulties in terms of the TAIS methodology.

1 Introduction and disclaimer

During 2020 and 2021, RAISD partners together with their Action Research Units (ARUs), formed by highly engaged stakeholders, committed to designing, implementing and establishing evaluation mechanisms for 8 Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAISs). Researchers, civil society organisations, Forcibly Displaced People (FDP), policy makers and a small number of persons from the business world that form the ARUs co-created pilot strategies in Spain, Italy, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan and Lebanon. These TAISs took place within the local contexts of the participating countries, each of which has a different national context, opinion climate and regulations in terms of welcoming and integrating FDP.

The expression "tailored" eloquently describes how these pilot experiences became different from the usual integration strategies used by organisations and institutions that assist FDP. First, as it happens when confectioning a suit, measures are taken and fabrics are analysed. In RAISD, this means detecting needs and requirements of forced migrants and detecting their vulnerabilities through interviews. Then, a tailor shows catalogues of different models of suits to the client. In RAISD, ARUs along with project researchers gathered and analysed best practices, with some of them giving ideas to the design of TAIS. After, the tailor makes a pattern for the suit with the collaboration of the client, cuts the fabric, sews and tries it on. In RAISD, the ARUs designed tailored strategies to attend to FDP's specific needs, tested and assessed them, and finally suggested these to FDP and other agents working in forced displacement.

The suit requires several rounds of trials where it is tailored to the figure and desires of the client. In RAISD, the TAIS design and execution was made in 3 successive iterations, with evaluations and adjustments between the phases for a better adjustment of the strategies to the specific needs of the target groups, above all FDP, but also social workers and organisations that benefited from the programs. Finally, if the suit is a success, the pattern model becomes part of the catalogue of the tailor and it is offered to other clients with similar characteristics. In RAISD, the TAISs are intended and offered for the use of similar projects and initiatives and therefore, they are included in the project dissemination and outreach strategy, of which the current deliverable forms part.

To offer a realistic picture of the TAIS methodology and guidelines put in practice, this deliverable takes a tour among the partner organisations' ARUS and TAIS, describing the benefits and challenges of the methodology that guides the TAIS process and evaluation and that is based on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), Action Research (AR) and Socio-Ecological Models (SEMs). Partners offer insights to the specific challenges, changes caused by local events and eventual ethical issues that arose along the TAIS process. To make the reading experience easier, each chapter includes a short resume followed by country specific information. A brief description of the methodological principles and guidelines is included to facilitate a comprehensive framework for the entire TAIS process.

DISCLAIMER: This deliverable is based on the information provided in the TAIS country reports that were submitted by the consortium members by mid November 2021, using an information gathering template collaboratively created by Menedék, the University of Helsinki (HU), CESIE, UNIMED and Complutense University of Madrid (UCM). Besides the country reports, information has been retrieved from other TAIS related documents and evidence at partners' disposal in the projects' internal worksite on a NextCloud platform.

The information provided for the current report D3.4 was found satisfactory in terms of TAIS methodology and its application by the partners, though slight imbalance was found in the extension and deepness of the answers.

It is also noteworthy that finding tailored solutions to the forced migrant attention and inclusion can be challenging, especially if the context and situation become more adverse. This points out the difficulty of aligning FDP's vulnerability context and needs with adequate and innovative TAIS pilots, due to several reasons like the local conditions of the FDP, the general opinion climate towards forced migrants, the TAIS work teams dynamics and efforts, as well as the unexpected global events such as the Covid-19 outbreak or the economic and political crises in several participating countries. More information and partners' insights about the challenges and difficulties about the TAIS methodology, design and execution can be found in chapter 4. From re-design to practice.

2 8 TAIS pilot experiences in a nutshell

The main working hypothesis in the RAISD project is that effective and appropriate strategies of attention and inclusion to highly Vulnerable Groups (VGs) of FDP need to be tailored to their specific Vulnerability Context (VC). Therefore, the project developed 8 TAIS pilots for the vulnerable persons among the forcibly displaced.

What is a TAIS?

TAIS is the acronym for "Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies". It means implementing a personalised attention and inclusion activity, that is, designed to respond to the specific needs of one of the VGs detected after working in the ARUs. TAISs are innovative and tailored as they define effective practices (i.e. highly scored by stakeholders and researchers' criteria) for a given context describing the correspondence between VCs, implemented practices and criteria for their evaluation.

The time assigned in the project was around 16 months, with 3 evaluation rounds every 4 months, from Spring 2020 to Winter 2021/22. In each round, the teams studied the evolution of the social intervention project and implemented the necessary improvements according to the problems detected. This was done both at national level in the participating countries and also in three international cross-analysis workshops.

Who are the beneficiaries?

The beneficiaries of the different TAIS are the highly VGs among the FDP. The work methodology in RAISD is structured through the notion of 'vulnerability context' (VC).

The concept of VC considers the interplay between the features of FDP and hosting communities, their interactions, and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them.

The project also emphasises the reciprocal nature of the work method, which transforms the collective 'victims' into active participants that are included in the collaborative design of the research. According to RAISD work methodology and guidelines (available in D3.2.), each ARU selected a VC that could be the beneficiary of its TAIS.

What is the role of the Action Research Units in the TAIS?

The seven ARUs were responsible for the development of the different TAISs. Therefore, RAISD team of each partner together with the stakeholders of the ARU co-designed, executed and evaluated the diverse TAIS pilots. The organisational model was decided by and built by each ARU.

The TAIS were open to the participation of all the stakeholders that have been working in an ARU. The stakeholders that participated in the research and innovation action include the FDP, research community, policy makers, business sector and industry, the educational community, and civil society members (e.g. Non-Governmental Organisations - NGOs - and citizens) that work with refugees, internally displaced people, and asylum seekers.

As mentioned before, the project implements its strategy through its network of seven ARUs, where partners work in the everyday situations of VGs and their hosting communities. Therefore, the TAIS were designed and put in practice in the ARUs located in Spain, Italy, Hungary, Finland, Turkey, Lebanon, and Jordan.

The project team and the actors started by gathering information and demonstrating an implementable approach to TAISs. Thereafter, they addressed the deeper understanding of the contextual factors influencing outcomes, as well as the logics of the actors' involvement.

Each ARU worked collaboratively with as diverse stakeholders as possible, in order to comply with some of the activities of an RRI architecture process (Deblonde, 2015).

With this knowledge, a methodology for the analysis of VCs and the development of TAISs was designed and applied. In this way, the information used in the project comes mainly from the actors and beneficiaries themselves. Literature in the domain plays a secondary role. With this approach, real data from actual situations have guided the definition of contexts and related elements, instead of superimposing a priori categories.

The 8 TAIS in a nutshell

As one of the core activities and tangible results of RAISD, the TAISs have been explained in detail in nine project deliverables and the brief information exposed below can be found at the RAISD website (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/tais/>).

Table 1. The Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy pilots among RAISD partners. Source: Authors own creation based on <https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/tais/>

Partner	Country	TAIS	Description
	Spain	Refuge of power: Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program	In Spain, the TAIS consists of a training and counselling program for forcibly displaced Sub-Saharan women, providing them with the necessary skills for starting their own business, either individually or collectively.

Partner	Country	TAIS	Description
	Italy	All You Can Learn: Inclusion à la carte	The Italian TAIS focuses on forcibly displaced women, and it aims at providing them with online learning tools. The central idea behind the TAIS is to personalise online learning through “Digitalised Personal Pathways” (DPP), based on which FDPs can have control over their own learning process.
	Finland	I Multilingual online forum II Development of child-care services in Finnish reception centres	In Finland, the TAIS is designed in the form of two parallel pilot activities that target asylum seekers who are in a vulnerable situation. One target group is young men with no social connections, who will receive online peer support. The other target group is single parents with small children, who will be provided with new forms of childcare services in reception centres.
	Hungary	Trajectory monitoring toolbox for social workers working with refugees	In Hungary, the objective of the TAIS is to enhance refugees’ embeddedness in social structures. Social workers and service providers analyse individual cases in order to build a “Trajectory monitoring toolbox” of helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees.
	Turkey	Accessing and Participating in Basic Daily life Practices Through Monitoring	The TAIS in Turkey focuses on the monitoring of the social integration of vulnerable FDP. A series of workshops creates capacities and awareness for various stakeholders, especially social workers at the local municipality.
	Jordan	Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF)	The TAIS in Jordan aims at providing psychosocial support for refugees, together with online training about financial, legal and health awareness on a special online portal that helps FDP to participate in an interactive exchange of knowledge.
	Lebanon	Health 4 SEAD “Health, Social Emotional, Academic, Development”	The TAIS in Lebanon promotes health awareness among Syrian university students and refugees living in camps. The coronavirus emergency makes it necessary to combine simple awareness raising activities with a more strategic approach via training focusing on social and emotional wellbeing.

3 About the TAIS methodology

“The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy is based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team works as a network of Action Research Units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people’ involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, provide information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. The software platform CRIOS supports this collaboration providing integrated tools for collaborative work, online discussion, tailored search of information, data storage, and document mining (among other functionalities, analysis, information extraction and anonymization).” (adapted from <https://raisd-h2020.eu/the-project/>).

3.1 RRI, Action Research and socio ecological models as methodological framework

The design and readjustment of the TAIS is guided by the general RAISD project research strategy based on methodological triangulation. It comprehends RRI, AR, and SEMs. Besides, as a both theoretical and technical tool, gender mainstreaming is applied from a gender-sensitive perspective.

Figure 1. RAISD methodological triangulation. Source: UCM team’s own creation.

At the overall level, RAISD adopts an RRI approach (Owen et al., 2012). RRI focuses on the need of co-creating research activities where all the relevant stakeholders play an active role in its definition, execution and evaluation.

RRI dimensions of diversity and inclusion, anticipation and reflection, openness and transparency, as well as capacity of response and adaptive change are also key elements of the TAIS (Owen et al., 2013). Deep research ethics, democratic decision making and gender equity and focus are inherent to the RRI research and innovation philosophy.

How does Action Research contribute to the methodology?

The actual work in the units that conform the project follow an AR approach (Stringer, 2013). Such approach advocates the use of context dependent procedures that are developed through inquiry in the specific setting, instead of the application of general standardised practices. The project implements a specific participatory AR approach to study the VGs.

The anticipation and reflection of AR enable us to visualise the impact on society and reflect the underlying values and objectives of research in the short, medium, and long term.

This methodology guarantees that the project is flexible and that it can be adapted to the changes in the needs of the action research expressed by participants. This methodology is inclusive since it incorporates the opinions of the stakeholders and of the social groups that participate in the TAIS throughout the process. It implies making the project accessible to all stakeholders (including the social group of beneficiaries) in all its phases.

A detailed analysis of the benefits and difficulties of the AR approach is offered in chapter 4.1.

What are the Socio-ecological models?

The SEMs are intended to analyse a social setting in a holistic way, at different levels of abstraction and from different perspectives. They include three interconnected levels of intervention:

1. Micro level: individual / interpersonal. Family and affective-emotional context.
2. Meso level: institutional. Interactions with communities of origin, receiving communities during transit and at destination, contexts of local groups and associations, intervening aid organisations, etc.
3. Macro level: policy / law. It is very unlikely that we can achieve results at the macro level during the project.

Macro level vs. meso / micro level: the macro level is the context to consider all the time. Recommendations directed at the macro level can be written, but TAIS must be implemented at the meso / micro level. If an obstacle is found at the macro level, which makes a given TAIS proposal unfeasible, it must be modified to be feasible.

The application of the Socio-ecological modelling and these levels on the TAIS are detailed in the following chapter 3.2.

How is the entire TAIS R&I process and how are the work packages connected?

The following figure explains the TAIS creation, implementation and evaluation process. It also establishes the connections between WPs and provides the main deliverables where more information can be found.

Figure 2. TAIS process as a whole. Source: Author's own creation.

If we look into the internal architecture of the RAISD project, we can see that the TAIS are directly connected to the specific project objectives SO5 Elaboration of recommendations to develop attention and inclusion strategies tailored to VCs, SO6 Validation of TAIS and their methodology through pilots and SO8 Creation of an Observatory for the TAIS in the forced displacement (FD).

The TAIS are to some extent related to all the project WPs, with a tighter interrelation with WP4 Vulnerability profiling, WP5 Design of Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies, WP6 Action Research development and WP7 Cross-analysis (TAIS evaluation). The TAIS Methodology is developed within WP3 Methodological coordination, of which the current deliverable D3.4 forms part. The TAIS follow the guidelines of WP1 Ethics requirements and are under the supervision of WP2 Project management, as all the project WPs. They also have a link with WP8 Collaborative research tool that provides a practical tool for further data analysis and storage, and with WP9

Dissemination that manages the research transparency and communication aspects, as well as the exploitation of the results.

The TAIS process started at the very beginning of the project, with the establishment of the ARUs that would contribute to all phases of the TAIS, this being the initial point for starting WP6 work in AR development. The ARUs assisted the local research teams in performing interviews to VGs among FDP in all the participating countries and in establishing vulnerability profiles that would later contribute to the definition of VCs, which was the core task of WP4. Altogether, 178 interviews to forcibly displaced people were carried out, including 25 interviewees in each of the participating countries: Spain, Italy, Turkey, Hungary, Lebanon and Jordan, with the exception of Finland, that included 28 interviews (more information at <https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/vulnerabilities/>). In terms of vulnerabilities found, these vary depending on the local context and type of migrants interviewed, but there are some common features. These include trauma as a result of the often long and troublesome migration journey, during which many have suffered physical and sexual violence, have witnessed murders, forced labour and slavery. The majority have migrated by irregular means, victims of human trafficking, human smuggling and dangerous death threading journeys by sea or land. Libyan camp and detention centre survivors share terrifying stories of human rights violations and extreme violence. Another factor that augments the vulnerability of many of these FDP is the lack of education, the school drop-out due to war and poverty are frequent among them. The fate of the ones with further education is usually better and they feel better integrated. Also, many have large families to support either with them or back in the home country. Many families have been torn apart in the exile process, some have lost family members who have been killed or kidnapped in the conflict areas. PTSD (post-traumatic stress disorder) and other psychological disorders are therefore frequent among them, though many do not mention these aspects directly. Also, many migrants suffer from chronic and other diseases, some are the result of the hardness and lack of proper food and sanitation conditions during the journey.

Most of the interviewees are asylum seekers and subsist with very scarce income, unemployment among them is extended and so is the adaptation to the transit or hosting countries society. Many migrants found life better in their home countries and feel nostalgic, though there are cases of extreme suffering and trauma experienced back in the old country which makes them want to forget everything about their origin, making them feel more at safe in the new country. A rather small number of the persons interviewed have started to feel integrated in the new country and are grateful for the assistance they receive from the authorities and NGOs. The vast majority have complaints about the asylum process and many offer ideas for its improvement. Not all have access to assistance programs, though many are included in the compulsory integration paths.

Within WP4 Vulnerability profiling, the first step was establishing several types of vulnerability profiles, based on the findings of the field research -the FDP interviews-, completed by information from current literature and reports. Then, the ARU members selected among the vulnerable groups and persons who work with FDP those profiles that would become the beneficiaries of the future TAIS, considering the urgency of their needs and the feasibility of action in every country. The ARUS then co-designed, with the participation of the target groups, the most suitable integration strategies, tailored to the specific needs and vulnerability profile of the beneficiaries, taking up the core activity of WP5, the establishment of the TAIS.

One of the core results of RAISD project is the novel and operative definition of Vulnerability Context (VC) and guidelines for detecting diverse vulnerability contexts within forced displacement, gathered in D4.2 vulnerability context: definition and guidelines (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>). WP4 outcomes give conceptual and contextual background and a better understanding of why a tailored approach is needed for each type of FDP attention strategy, facilitating WP5 and WP6 work in designing, evaluating and re-designing the TAIS in collaboration with the ARUS. The approximation to the novel concept of the VC, its definition, conceptual construct and elements are explained in D4.2 Vulnerability context: definition and guidelines. Menedék has gathered in D5.3 (TAIS definition and Guidelines) insights on the VC practical application in the TAIS definition and guidelines:

“The TAIS implementations themselves provided the RAISD team with a new perspective on understanding the nature of vulnerability from the project planning angle. The plans of the pilot interventions all had to deal with a question of ‘in what vulnerability contexts are we able to facilitate change in the given conditions.’ So, from this feasibility perspective arose the need to look at the matrix with a new approach and create another classification of vulnerability context. In the case of the RAISD project, it is possible to use the following – less theoretical but more practical – dichotomy”. (p. 26-27).

As stated by Menedék, both types of elements interfere in the context of a vulnerable person and limit the person's options in a given situation, moment and place.

- A (rather) Dynamic vulnerability element. The main characteristic is its ability to change regardless of the available resources.

Examples: housing questions, labour market integration issues, communication limitations, obstacles to services, emergency cases, coping strategies, education.

- A (rather) Static vulnerability element. The main characteristic is its difficulty (or impossibility) to change.

Examples: the individual's broader macro environment. Hostile political and social circumstances, lack of services. How the individual appears in the matrix: nature or characteristics (e.g., shyness). The condition or circumstance (e.g., unaccompanied minor, traumatised, single parent). Pre-migration resources (human, social, economic, and cultural capital). Individual socio-demographic profile.

When designing the TAIS, ARU members and TAIS service providers together with the implementation team needed to understand the VC that surrounds the beneficiary FDP groups. Besides looking at vulnerability context primarily from the viewpoint of the vulnerable group, it is essential to analyse it with the dynamic-static spectrum in mind and consider what aspects related to the context might be expected to experience change or can be improved and what remains static and conditions the life of FDP. Macro level elements, such as a hostile central or a local government that does not favour FDP integration can hinder forced migrants opportunities for getting a work permit or make it difficult for an NGO to recruit volunteers and raise funds. A detailed analysis of the VC related to the TAIS activity in diverse socio-ecological levels is offered in D5.3 TAIS: Definition and guidelines.

Previously, WP5 had produced a deliverable on good practices, D5.1 Catalogue of Attention and Inclusion Practices, that served as inspiration for the design of the TAISs. The RAISD Good Practices analysis had the intention to evaluate past and current inclusion initiatives across the European Union influence area, – characterised in terms of target

group, objectives, requirements, type of host community, actual results, evaluation by actors, related artefacts – and to ultimately support the ARUs in shaping new and innovative Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced. These inclusion practices highlight numerous connections in terms of helping, assisting, mentoring, educating, and providing services to refugees and vulnerable populations; the selection process included the identification of actor-oriented criteria that each practice should meet (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/observatories/good-practices/>).

Then, following the methodological guidelines of WP3, the TAIS started their activity, with 3 cycles of action followed by successive evaluations rounds in each country, after which the necessary adjustments were incorporated to the TAIS designs. During these rounds, WP6 AR was aligned with WP5 TAIS design, where the ARUs carried out AR activities to evaluate and improve the TAIS, and participated in the WP5 weekly TAIS activities, mostly in trainings. D7.1 Research stories describe ARUs engagement in the project and in the TAIS and D6.2 Report on the implementation of the TAIS in the ARUs traces an important part of these activities (both available at <https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>). WP5 also offered capacity building courses for TAIS implementers, ARU members and other stakeholders working in forced displacement and with FDP (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/observatories/capacity-building/>). Within WP5, two deliverables define, describe and catalogue the TAIS: D5.3 TAIS definition and guidelines and D5.4 Catalogue of TAISs (available soon at <https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>).

WP7 Cross analysis was responsible for the shared evaluation and explained to partners the actor-oriented criteria to be used in TAIS evaluation, contained in D7.3 Evaluation criteria -preliminary version- and D7.4 Evaluation criteria -final version, (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>). Within WP7, CESIE organised 3 international workshops for the participatory evaluation of the TAISs at global level, with participants of the ARUs and Advisory Board (AB) members from the partner countries, the results of which have been included in D7.2 Cross pilot workshop reports (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>). The results mostly show positive process and outcome evaluations, with some room for improvement especially in terms of financial planning and more engagement of the FDP in the management process.

Guidelines for those stakeholders interested in adopting approaches similar to the TAISs will be offered in D3.5 Recommendations on the adoption of a TAIS-oriented approach (due May 2022, will be available soon at <https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>). To the coordination team's knowledge, apart from the consortium members, several ARU members are already using a TAIS-oriented approach in new activities.

How are the TAIS evaluated?

Before designing a TAIS, the following criteria were considered:

- Specific: what the TAIS plans to achieve must be very clear.
- Measurable: its development must be properly defined and measured through indicators.
- Achievable: the objectives must be established proportionally at micro and meso levels (contributions of time and money must provide sufficient results).
- Relevant: the TAIS must be related to the vulnerability and the existing needs based on the interviews and previous work of the ARU.

- Based on time: a complete project cycle must be planned, and the time frame must be realistic / feasible.
- Sustainable: indicators that enable their duration in the medium and long term must be identified.

TAIS evaluation is based on an actor-oriented definition of indicators. The indicators for the TAIS are discussed in terms of the following categories:

- a) Hierarchy: input/output – outcome/result – impact.

It is suggested that lower level indicators should be set (input/output).

- b) Perspective: process-oriented – result-oriented.

It is suggested that result-oriented indicators should be given priority.

- c) Evaluation: baseline, interim, final.

It is suggested that baseline and final are a must, interim indicators only if reasonable.

The exact evaluation criteria should be set up individually for each TAIS by its participants, in line with RAISD's WP7. The evaluation criteria were fully detailed in previous D7.3 Evaluation criteria -preliminary version- and D7.4 Evaluation criteria -final version.

3.2 Socio ecological levels of the TAIS

The TAIS in the seven participating countries mainly took place at the micro and meso socio-ecological levels, as activities aimed at improving the beneficiaries' situation, knowledge and capacities, in their individual, family or professional settings. Several of the TAIS also fostered forced migrants' social engagement, their relation and involvement both with organisations that assist FDP and general legal, health and social life related institutions in their environment. Macro level policymaking was not directly contemplated in the actual design and execution of the TAISs, but contributions and ideas sometimes popped up in the lapse of the activities, especially during the TAIS evaluation rounds and in the collaborative workshops. These co-working sessions, carried out all along the project and where all the stakeholder groups were invited to express their ideas, provided a fruitful ground for seed ideas that might turn into policy recommendations (collected in D9.9 Policy brief). Some of the meso level effects that have the potential of contributing to policy recommendations are worth mentioning, among others the increased overall HVG participation in the design and implementation of the attention programs (due to the co-design approach), reduction of the usually high dropout among HV female participants (due to the gender approach) and provision of tested strategy ideas for vulnerable groups (due to the tailored strategy approach).

Still, most of the TAIS pilots act only in micro and meso levels, they may become relevant benchmarking actions for the reception centres and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) that work in migrant integration and assistance, though these actions have reduced potential of influencing integration policies and will have mostly meso and micro level effects. The advocacy action, e.g. when it comes to partners and other stakeholders publishing about the TAISs and project findings in relevant media, is also an interesting example of the indirect effects of the TAISs that can be considered macro level impacts, which might even have effects at policy level (or at least raising the awareness of

the policy makers about the importance of tailored strategies). In most cases, the TAISs also contributed to spreading the word about FDP rights among diverse stakeholders.

Next, a brief introduction to these TAISs and their main aspects follow.

In Spain, micro level actions and effects were the most relevant for the TAIS beneficiaries, forced migrant background African women, especially the improvement of their professional baggage and abilities for job seeking and entrepreneurship, better self-reliance and autonomy and a more holistic picture of their own rights and situation in Spain.

In Italy, the All You Can Learn (AUCL) program had efficacy both at micro and meso levels. For the HVGs, it basically meant increased participation, enhanced decision-making capacity, augmented abilities and self-confidence, more opportunities or self-help and peer support (micro level), whereas for the professionals and organisations involved in the trainings the benefits were in terms of enhanced quality of staff and services, optimised efforts adapted to the learners' needs and flexibility in the training provision methods (meso level).

In Finland, there were two TAISs. TAIS I had impacts on micro and individual level as it fostered relationship among asylum seekers and volunteers, but it also impacted on meso level as a benchmark activity among the Finnish reception system; TAIS II, the childcare service, had effects both on the micro and meso levels: it improved the autonomy of asylum-seeking families and offered a new service for the Finnish reception system.

In Hungary, the TAIS impacted mostly on meso level. Their beneficiaries were social workers, and the TAIS helped them in the professional deepening and sharing their professional burden.

In Turkey, the training impacted on a micro level as it helped refugees, especially Syrian women, to tackle the difficulties they face in their daily lives, due to the language, economic and cultural barriers. Furthermore, it improved the knowledge and attitudes of the municipal social workers that participated in the training. It also had effect on meso level, as it brought together local host communities and refugees, governments and NGOs, to search for shared solutions.

In Jordan, the PRSF worked both at micro and meso levels: at micro levels, the refugees benefitted from psychological and social support and the families gained awareness on their legal rights, whereas at the meso level the program directed the attention of the NGO's to the refugee's psychological needs and the Refugee Support System (RSS) portal benefitted the organisations in terms of dissemination of their activities.

In the Lebanese case, the Health 4 SEAD program was geared to engage refugee students in Covid-19 awareness and prevention, as well as to get academic and emotional support to FDP. Thus, its main effects were at the micro level, but also some meso level aspects were relevant, as the refugee students who had been trained in the program received an empowering effect, as they could further transfer their knowledge to peers in Syrian camps and schools.

In the following, we offer more detailed information on the TAIS activity and effects in the project countries, in the 3 before mentioned socio ecological levels.

Spain

Micro level:

In terms of the Spanish TAIS, individual/familiar conditions of the beneficiaries (competence level in new technologies and availability of digital devices, competence level of Spanish, work or study hours and other responsibilities...) have been considered for the schedule and content of the program.

The beneficiaries have improved their use of new technologies, this has a direct impact on providing them with new tools to communicate with other people, both in their place of origin, country of destination or any new environment they face. The program has also improved their social relationships as they have been in contact with peers during the pandemic and the total lockdown. Improving their social support network has been also considered by means of the TAIS, generating a support network among women from different places of origin and with different mother tongues. Finally, some of them have developed friendship ties with each other.

Throughout the training and the mentoring program, an attempt was made to improve their autonomy and responsibility for their self-learning, avoiding behaviours of dependence on the workers of the entities or third parties. By means of some practical activities, and when the Covid-19 health situation allowed it, the beneficiaries were asked to interact with their social environment or neighbourhood. For example, looking for and observing small businesses similar to a business idea they wanted to develop in their surroundings.

Through the training and evaluation rounds of the TAIS, they have developed their capacity for reflection, constructive criticism regarding the activity and also self-criticism about their performance. Within the training, the beneficiaries have worked on identifying and developing their own personal strengths.

Meso level:

Beneficiaries' level of user skills in new technologies has improved, which also improves their communication and relationship with different entities and with the administration, increasing their social and personal autonomy. Precisely, one of the aims has been to improve their knowledge of bureaucratic aspects in order to learn to interact with different organisations in a much more proactive way.

One of the main objectives of the TAIS has been to improve their ability to enter the labour market or to improve their employment situation. Beneficiaries have been helped to guide their expectations regarding job search, and have been assisted in their training to be autonomous, develop a business plan, entrepreneurship and mentoring to search for paid work. The training has included contents on gender aspects and human and labour rights.

Information on current social and health issues, such as complex and changing movement restrictions in Madrid, has also been shared. Individual protection measures (masks) were provided.

Meso level has been considered specifically as TAIS has been co-designed with public and public-funding organisations, as well as private NGOs, that are responsible for official measures and programs for the inclusion of refugees and asylum-seekers in Spain. Moreover, some of these representatives affirm that they have reflected, for example, on the process of design and evaluation of their own care and inclusion strategies, showing interest in adopting some aspects in their organisations.

All these micro and meso aspects, as well as their evolution, were monitored by a social worker hired under the project. For example, considering the results of the TAIS, their learning process, (personal, technological, understanding...) problems and challenges that they had and the new ones that were emerging.

Macro level:

Though the TAIS was adjusted to the micro and meso level conditions (above all the real needs and abilities of the beneficiaries), macro level issues related to the pandemic had serious consequences not only on the health and social situation of the participants, but also on their economic level (a very uncertain time to launch a new business with the closure of many small and medium-sized businesses).

Macro-level policies were not part of the TAIS design. However, the improvements in the computer skills of the beneficiaries also imply a possibility to access new information sources and explore their situation from a broader perspective, not only as a means of obtaining practical information for their paperwork, but also learning about national and international migration policies via organisational websites. This wider knowledge together with their firsthand experience in migration, enables them to provide not only micro and meso, but also macro-level recommendations. As a result of this personal experience and their participation in the TAIS, the beneficiaries have also been asked to reflect on possible policy recommendations in the attention and inclusion of FDP.

Italy

The Italian TAIS was designed to mainly affect FDP environments and vulnerabilities at micro and meso level, but indirectly impacting on the macro level.

Micro level:

The Italian TAIS micro level aspects can be seen through <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/learn>

Among the main effects on the HVG among FDP were the following: increased participation and satisfaction in learning; enhanced individual decision-making capacity and critical attitude; developed ability and self-confidence when creating their Action-Plan; decreased initial resistance and attendance reluctance to join a learning experience; kept opportunities for Self-help and peer support; and finally, provided concrete opportunities to learn something new to enter the labour market.

Meso level:

The meso level aspects are visible at <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/teach>

The meso level activities focused on FDP/HVG relief and support through community and Extraordinary Reception Centres (Centri di Accoglienza Straordinaria in Italy, CAS). The activities had effects on aspects such as efficiency of local support networks, monitoring “users” situations and conditions, and ability to report or address HVG to associations, stakeholders and local authorities that offer specific and specialised services.

Professional educators, including schools, training centres, teachers, trainers, cultural mediators and volunteers also received benefits from the TAIS program, in terms of enhanced quality of staff and offered services, optimised efforts in identifying trainees’ learning needs and avoided dispersion of resources, info and data (learners’ profiling and

mapping), and finally, achieved flexibility in training provision methods (update and adapt traditionally excessive strictness of the paths and hours of commitment).

In terms of the quintuple helix stakeholders, ARUs and further the ARU Observatory, we can mention effects in terms of improved alignment to real HVG learning needs when designing future training opportunities and programmes, fostered comprehensive interdisciplinary perspective of territorial networking and cooperation procedures, and ensured fair accessibility to territorial inclusion-service environment.

Macro level:

Macro level effects can be seen at <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org>

Many of the activities carried out in the micro and meso levels have indirect effects on authorities and institutions, as well as other policy makers, such as Increased HVG participation in education and training, reduced high shares of female HVG NEET (people not in employment, education or training) TAIS activity dropouts, pursued inclusive attention policy for specific socially Vulnerable Groups and fostered inclusion and responsiveness in hosting communities.

Finland

As seen in chapter 2, Finland carried out two different TAIS programs: a multilingual online forum for asylum seeking and Finnish speaking men, and a childcare service for reception centres.

Micro and meso levels:

The online forum took primarily place on micro and individual levels. The focus was on individual asylum seekers and voluntary persons and promotion of the relations between the two groups. However, there was also a stress on meso levels in the form of the Finnish Red Cross and reception system as institutions. One of the aims of the TAIS was to encourage these institutions to benefit from new ways to see voluntary work and online methods as parts of the reception services.

The TAIS consisting in childcare services mainly took place on micro and meso levels. The main aim of the developmental work was to promote the autonomy and context-specific capabilities of asylum-seeking families, both parents and children. Therefore, the TAIS affected mainly on individual and family levels (micro). Moreover, the TAIS was an intervention to professional and institutional practices in the context of the Finnish reception system (meso). Developmental work of the TAIS aimed to promote extra-statutory activities in reception centres thus redirecting the professional routines and practices.

Macro level:

Finally, in the best-case scenario and in the long run, successful TAIS may provoke changes in the macro levels as well. A successful outcome would be, in particular, to guarantee the right to early childhood education in municipal day-care centres for asylum-seeking families. In Finland, discussion on asylum seekers' right to day care is currently ongoing and during the project, the capital of Finland granted asylum-seeking children a right to municipal day-care services. Advocacy work based on TAIS was done by writing an opinion piece in a national newspaper and interaction with the Ministry of Education and culture.

Hungary

In Hungary, the political context continues to be hostile, and the service-providing structures are in a difficult situation. Weakness of institutions and inter-institutional coordination in the social sphere, as well as the difficult access to many institutions and services, have a negative effect on the vulnerability of the forcibly displaced. As a result, many people fall out of the scope of supportive services because complex problems cannot be tackled by one service provider alone. Macro level changes in this environment were impossible for the TAIS to achieve.

Micro and meso level:

The TAIS took place on the meso level and potentially affected the micro level. The emphasis was on the interpersonal and individual conditions of the beneficiaries: for social workers and other helpers, "reviewing" cases, reflecting on them, may bring professional deepening and the possibility of supervision. More importantly, on the service provider side, it was crucial to consider the emotional burden on social workers. A personalised approach helped prevent "vicarisation" i.e. when emotional burden takes its toll on the social worker. It is crucial to mention that long-term and sustainable development within the Hungarian system can only be achieved at the meso level.

Due to the above mentioned hostile political environment, state-run programs are not visible due to the law changes that took place from June 2016 onwards. Since then, the engagement in the field of integration services between state institutions (the Immigration Office or the Family Support Centres) gradually decreased, and in June 2018, it was eliminated. Also, the similar or substitute services financed from the Asylum, Migration, and Integration Fund, such as housing programs, language courses, labour market integration support, were phased-out. In this context, it was impossible to achieve sustainable change at the micro level.

Turkey

In summary, the Turkish TAIS had effects in the micro and meso levels. This TAIS was designed considering the obstacles that refugees often face in their daily life in Turkey.

Micro level:

Many of the refugees in Turkey face various challenges regarding the language, the nationality and their economic status. This situation negatively affects the integration process of refugees with the host society. The situation gets even more difficult when it comes to refugee women. When the patriarchal values of both the society those refugees come from, in this case mainly Syrian society, and the Turkish society, which is the host, combine with the difficulties of being a refugee, refugee women find themselves in a highly vulnerable and disadvantaged position among forcibly displaced groups limiting their capabilities to access their fundamental rights in accessing to daily life practices. Based on these points, the TAIS has effects on micro level activities.

Meso level:

The trainings provided within the scope of TAIS also has a significant impact on local government and NGO representatives, as well as persons active in business life. Bringing members of the host community and refugees together to express their views on inclusion and diversity issues enabled these institutions to reflect on what they can do about these issues. Thus, local level policy makers and business representatives can decide to carry out

additional activities at the institutional level after this TAIS implementation and convey this to the competent authorities. In this respect, this TAIS is implemented with the support and attendance of representatives of governmental and non-governmental organisations, experts, members of host society and FDP, so the effects mainly took place on micro and meso levels.

Macro level:

Although the outcomes of the TAIS are expected to activate efforts towards revisions in local regulations regarding refugees, the main effects should be considered on micro and meso levels rather than macro level.

Jordan

The TAIS effect took place on the micro (individual/family) level, meso (organisational) level, and macro (policymaking) level.

Micro level:

On the individual level, refugees, identified as VGs among FDP, benefited from the implemented services tailored to their needs. The psychological and social support provided refugees with services that contributed to enhancing their well-being starting with their acceptance and inclusion in the host community. The services also were directed to empower refugees on economic, legal, social, health, and psychological conditions and barriers. The TAIS helped in raising awareness among refugees about the importance of psychological support as a preventive measure instead of the need for medical intervention. The psychological support system portal (RSS) helps refugees in getting access to psychological support among other communal services directed towards refugees and locals in the host community.

On the familial level, the implemented services provided families with the necessary knowledge of their legal rights. It also directed them to find means and ways to psychologically support themselves as family members through the economic, health, and social empowerment workshops.

Meso level:

The implemented services along with the methods, practices and training programs were shared with NGOs participating in RAISD project in order to direct their attention to the refugees' psychological needs and priorities. The RSS portal benefits the NGOs to disseminate their programs and activities along with studies conducted by researchers. As the RSS creates an appropriate environment for information storage, NGOs capitalise this portal to process and protect their information as it is a medium that protects refugees' data. There are few organisations that provide psychological support to VGs, even if it is not comprehensive. Unfortunately, such services are submitted according to the proposed projects for a certain period of time only and for a certain number of persons, and the programs are not long-term regarding the follow-up of the situation until people reach safety or a clear change in their ability to overcome the experiences they have gone through. In this sense, NGOs utilise this portal to fill their information and services for dissemination purposes regarding their activities, programs and training to serve psychological support.

Macro level:

Jordan has extensive experience in dealing with various refugees' crisis over the years and this has provided important lessons to the international community. Refugees and migrants must issue a work permit before starting work. Refugees do not have the right to work in government jobs and everything related to security and the army. Jordanian law guarantees the right of the worker and establishes strict norms that apply to Jordanian and non-Jordanian employees and workers alike. Nevertheless, there are some individual practices where employees and workers are exploited, not being paid enough and in accordance with the work. Unfortunately, refugees, due to their need and ignorance of Jordanian law, accept any amount of money as a salary. Such situations in the refugee life could make him/her with VG. Therefore, the implemented services, specifically within the economic and legal psychological support, spread awareness of refugees' rights and the country's policies, which assure decent living conditions for them. RSS also provides information regarding refugees and migration laws and regulations.

Lebanon

Micro-level:

For the training of the Syrian HE students, their competence level in leadership, digital media and communication through the medium of the English language have been contemplated. The implementation of digital device training in the digital literacies of the students imply a success in knowing how strong these students have improved in these skills.

It has been noted that the HE students have become better with the new tools to improve their communication with others especially at LIU, as shown in the videos about the trainings.

Moreover, TAIS has also provided them with the means to improve and develop their social support network in and outside the university as one of the girls pointed out in the video.

One of the observation tools of a learner is high expectation. Expectation of their learning process has been high during the course of the training program.

In resume, the TAIS program for the Syrian student had three phases: first, directing students in their studies (and knowledge building); second, coaching them and third, assisting them to become support members for their communities.

Meso-level:

The extent to which the Syrian HE (Higher Education) students are actively involved in new technologies has significantly improved. This in turn has resulted in an enhancement of their communication skills and provided them with competences to spread to knowledge among refugees. This micro level activity contributed to creating effect also in the organizational (meso) level, in the workplaces where the Syrian students work and teach.

The primary objective with regards to the Lebanese TAIS is centred to empower students in the working place, to enrich their employment status or dissemination to develop awareness in the Syrian camps and schools where they teach.

The meso level showed, for instance, rapid identification and safe referral to psychosocial, medical services, and in developing refugee and frontline worker capacity to better react to children' needs, including supporting participation in education.

Macro-level:

As a result of the unprecedented Covid-19 pandemic and political uprising in Lebanon, the amendment of TAIS had to be made as a consequence of both the micro and macro- level disputes. It should be noted that the pandemic resulted in serious consequences at the health, social, political and security levels in Lebanon.

3.3 Embedding gender approach to the TAIS practice

Gender approach is at the very core of the TAIS design and execution strategy, as many of the TAIS beneficiaries are forced migrant women that have suffered both physical and psychological gender-based violence. Being a woman or a girl is often a determinant factor that augments the vulnerability of a forced migrant. This is particularly evident in dangerous and violent home and transit country conditions (e.g. violation of basic human rights, raping, violence and human trafficking in Libya), but it also appears in receiving countries where the conditions often are not the expected, the atmosphere and attitudes towards FDP can be negative, and the asylum seeking and integration process become very difficult, depending on the national legislations. Many FDP drag from their journey several post trauma symptoms, complicated family conditions, loneliness, isolation, economic difficulties, local culture and language knowledge gaps, patriarchal family traditions, unwanted pregnancy... The list of challenges is long and here, gender acts in an intersectional way, often aggravating the situation when the context is difficult.

The University of Edinburgh's hub for gender and sexuality studies "Applying GSSA to your Project" (GenderED, 2022) offers a simplified tool for gender-sensitive situational analysis which offers some guidelines to the gender approach in the RAISD project. The initial setting requires equal access to decision making, to resources and their control and an egalitarian division of labour and human resources, as well as a gender-sensitive analysis of the starting point, the initial situation. Gender differences and equity are considered at diverse research stages, from the conceptualisation of the project, data collection and fieldwork, to building a balanced team and incorporating gender focus to impact assessment and dissemination as well as outcomes monitoring.

Figure 3. Gender-sensitive situational analysis. Source: GenderED, University of Edinburgh (<https://www.gender.ed.ac.uk/gender-sensitive-research/gssa-fivesteps/>)

If we place the TAIS in the Oxfam Rubric for Integrating gender (Jayasinghe, Pavez Butt & Zaaroura, 2019), most of them can be considered not only gender-sensitive, but also gender-responsive. Gender is considered in the project’s rationale and design, and the methodology is rigorously analysed with a gender view to inform implementation, communication and influencing strategies. To reach the upper level of becoming gender-transformative, the research and innovation need to address the underlying structural factors, such as norms and power relations that contribute to gender inequalities. This latter level has been reached to some extent in RAISD research, e.g. in the definition of the VC.

Gender is considered at all phases of the project, beginning with a gender-sensitive research and innovation design and gender equity in the workgroups. It impregnates the whole process from the fieldwork to the design, execution and evaluation of the TAISs. Gender is also used in the project conceptualization, as it is determinant in the understanding and definition of the concept of VC and in the language used by the project participants. Even if RAISD cannot be considered a fully gender-transformative project, at conceptual level and in terms of most of the national TAIS programs, it pretends to empower forced displaced women and foster gender equity and inclusion, and to become a project with a potential benchmark effect, as it offers a pathway to gender equal and inclusive work environments and gender transformative integration practices

Gender-blind	Gender (the differentiated and intersectional experiences of women, men, and gender diverse groups) is not considered in the research project; not even its conceptualisation or its rationale.
Gender-aware	Gender is considered in the research project's rationale but is not an operative concept in the design and methodology.
Gender-sensitive	Gender is considered in the research project's rationale, project design and methodology. Data is disaggregated by gender, and gender is also considered in the composition of the research team and reviewers. Gender-sensitive research does not (yet) extend to analysis and action to address gender inequalities.
Gender-responsive	Gender is considered in the research project's rationale, design and methodology and is rigorously analysed with a view to inform implementation, communication, and influencing strategies. Gender-responsive research does not (yet) address the underlying structural factors such as norms and power relations that contribute to gender inequalities.
Gender-transformative	Examines, analyses, and builds an evidence base to inform long-term practical changes in structural gender power relations and norms, roles and inequalities. Gender-transformative research should lead to sustained change through action (e.g., partnerships, outreach, and interventions, particularly with women's right organisations).

Figure 4. Oxfam Rubric for Integrating Gender in Research Planning. Source: Integrating gender in research planning. Oxfam International. <https://acortar.link/EGHPb7>. © Oxfam International.

Embedding gender to any research and innovation projects' structures, power relationships, methods, execution and evaluation is not an easy task. This project provides important insights and practical advice about these issues in several internal and public documents (more information in D3.2.2 Manual researcher: Ethics and Gender and other documents at <https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>).

In order to design a gender-sensitive research project, gender aspects should be transversally integrated in the research design and structures and monitored throughout the project. The experience with the RAISD research and the TAIS process have provided some practical insights about embedding gender into a project. The main steps to be considered include the following:

1. Build inclusive research and implementation teams, with equal gender balance, ensuring you include 50 % of women.
2. Consider including a wider gender and inclusion perspective, integrating Lesbian, Gay, Transgender, Bisexual, Intersex and Queer or Questioning (LGTBIQ) aspects when feasible. Consider including non-binary persons in the team and in the design.
3. Give both/all genders a say and include an equal number of men and women in management and decision-making positions, including access and control to resources. Make sure the inclusion is reflected in action.

4. Make a gender-sensitive research design: from situation analysis to data collection, fieldwork and data analysis. Reflect about gender as a factor, underlying variable or explaining element.
5. Explore gender differences when reporting results, see if these are descriptive or explanatory.
6. Search for intersectionalities and conceptualise gender in your work. For example, see how it correlates with other vulnerability aspects.
7. Acknowledge gender aspects and equitable participation in project dissemination, outreach and exploitation activities.
8. Monitor gender-related aspects all along the project process and correct deviations.
9. Aim to offer far reaching results in terms of gender equity. If possible, move from gender-sensitive to gender-transformative action.
10. Give gender-transformative policy recommendations when feasible.
11. Share your experience and spread good practices.

Our pretension next is to share some of the partners ideas and practices when integrating the gender focus in the TAIS and their pilots.

Spain

Gender was a key element and it is transversally embedded in the whole TAIS research and innovation process in Spain. The team started with a gender-sensitive situational analysis, where gender differences were considered when exploring the concept of VGs among FDP, detecting VGs as possible beneficiaries of the TAIS. Gender can be considered an intersectional element that correlates with other aspects of vulnerability.

Gender was considered in both data collection and fieldwork: Female interviewers trained in gender issues and attitudinal capacities were used for the interviews with FDP women (gender match), and the data analysis was gender-sensitive.

Fostering female participation in the research teams was a key element of gender within the Spanish research and ARU teams, including aspects such as decision making, access and control of resources, division of labour and female leadership. The composition of participants in the ARU meetings in Spain was balanced, often with a bit more female participants. The TAIS execution team was entirely formed by women, as were all the beneficiaries. The project as a whole has shared leadership between men and women, though the female participants in the core team outscore men (6 to 2). Both the TAIS and the core RAISD teams had several gender experts.

Gender and diversity was contemplated from a wide perspective. The participation of non-binary people and transsexual women in the collection of information and the design of the TAIS has been sought. In fact, a transsexual FDP has actively participated in several ARU meetings.

Conceptualization of gender and intersectionality of gender are key concepts in forced migration studies. These concepts have been carefully considered when working on the definitions of core ideas and results of the project, such as the novel idea about VC.

When it comes to potential impacts and dissemination of the TAIS, the objective has been empowering the female beneficiaries, acknowledging their advances during the training, as well as giving tribute to the persons engaged in the training. Also, when disseminating the final results of the project and the TAIS, emphasis is placed on how the gender dimension has been included throughout the process.

Monitoring of outcomes and processes is vital for the proper application of the gender perspective. As project coordinator, UCM team has made several reminders and specific guides on the application of gender in the research and in the design and execution of the TAIS. Also, gender issues often arise in the Consortium meetings and ARU workshops where the TAISs were discussed. The UCM team has also considered gender as a cross-cutting aspect within the TAIS set of evaluation criteria. All practical aspects related to gender have been taken into account by the social worker of the UCM team when analysing the needs and challenges of the beneficiaries of the TAIS.

Early-stage researchers were trained in gender issues via direct mentoring of the gender experts in the team and were engaged in research and dissemination activities. Students and volunteers of the project have received informal training on gender. The TAIS beneficiaries received lessons on gender and gender-related rights.

Structural changes related to gender balance should be the ultimate goal in the gender-transformative approach. Though the TAIS has not directly worked on the underlying structural and power relations related to gender, the training has called the participants' attention to aspects related to gender equity and equal rights.

Italy

In Italy, the gender perspective was transversally used in the whole research and TAIS processes. <https://cesie.org/en/higher-education-and-research/gender-sensitive-approaches-responsible-research-innovation/>

A gender-sensitive approach was applied in research. The AUCL selective-learning approach has been designed to respond to forcibly displaced (highly) vulnerable individuals with migratory background, for both female and male learners' needs. When formulating the research question, both men and women were considered and it was also analysed if and in what way men and women could be relating differently to the research problem.

RAISD provided the opportunity to pilot the approach, this time, with all highly vulnerable female participants – though its design is suitable to be adopted by a variety of other specific profiles too. The offer of learning outcomes and the training methodology is relevant and adaptable to benefit lives of highly vulnerable individuals with specific needs that might depend on age, gender, nationality, level of education and employment. In terms of sustainability, the Italian ARU Observatory has the tools to check if and how different vulnerable profiles use the project results in different ways.

A gender-sensitive approach was also applied in the AUCL curriculum. The team of trainers was composed of a balanced number of female and male staff and the invited visiting guest speaker Asma Baashe Hassan is renowned for her gender-sensitivity. Asma was invited as a guest speaker for her personal life experience: a Somali girl, faced the journey of human trafficking through Libya. She herself experienced the Libyan detention camps and faced the journey by boat to Italy. When she arrived in Italy, she was destined to a centre for minors, and after completing her journey in the community, she based all her energies on educational growth. She enrolled in a high school and is now

studying at university. Her path of emancipation, study, research and independence was considered exemplary and to be shared with the participants of the RAISD project.

The learning outcomes explicitly relate to the gender topic in terms of inequalities in society, and trainers have consulted for gender-sensitive studies while preparing the educational materials for the piloting.

AUCL produced gender-sensitive hand-out publications ([Trainees' Diary](#)) and used gender-sensitive language and visual materials while teaching and writing course materials. A proof-reading in both language versions was done to ensure the used language avoids projecting stereotypical gender roles.

AUCL devoted a full section at its website to "Social cohesion, equity and equality" (15 learning-outcomes: from LO.39 to LO.54), openly approaching the gender dimension to increase awareness about stereotypes and inequalities in different vulnerability contexts.

A gender-sensitive approach was also applied in the AUCL needs analysis (fieldwork). To ensure gender balanced data gathering on vulnerabilities among FDP living in Sicily (in transit or as final destination) during fieldwork following the SEMs in 2019, one female and one male researcher were employed to carry out the interviews. The following methodological criteria were adopted during the selection process:

- Researchers with a refugee or migrant background, or from the same culture.
- Gender match with interviewees.
- Experience in interviewing vulnerable groups.
- Trained on gender and intercultural issues.
- Trained on attitudinal procedures for interviews dynamisation (avoiding ethnocentrism, fostering trust relationships, care and sensitivity, security issues, procedures for incidental findings, etc.).

The profiles of the selected researchers were:

- Female researcher: originally from Kenya, living in Italy for 25 years. Intercultural mediator and translator for a Jesuit migrant/community centre. Former trainee at CESIE.
- Male researcher: originally from Senegal, living in Italy for 20 years. Professional cultural mediator and translator for Western African dialect at Territorial Commissions of Trapani and Palermo, work experiences at Intersos-Unicef and the National Institute for Health, Migration and Poverty (INMP).

Finland

Gender perspective has been deeply integrated in the Finnish sub-project and the two TAIS implemented here throughout the project. The online forum was designed to match the needs of young single men (comprising the vast majority of asylum seekers in Finland), while the development of childcare services was designed for parents (mostly women) with small children. In addition to the fundamental starting point, there has been no significant adjustments from the gender perspective during the piloting rounds. However, some small adjustments have taken place in this sense. Asylum seeking men have not been highly eager to talk about their feelings or personal experiences in Finland. Of course, the online platform and lingual issues probably have something to do with this as well. There has been more need in discussing concrete aspects and needs related to employment and education.

The gender perspective is also at the core of the second Finnish TAIS. This TAIS was designed for the parents of small children and even though both fathers and mothers are included, mothers tend to have more care responsibility in families with two parents, and many single parents in reception centres are mothers. Moreover, mothers - and women in general - with certain national backgrounds tend to be more often illiterate, as their education has not been supported by local structures in their countries of origin. In Finland, as in other European countries as well, women with a migration background are in public discussions repeatedly blamed for non-integration to the labour market, while the structural obstacles – such as lack of child-care services in the reception period – are often ignored. Therefore, the TAIS developing child-care services in reception centres is contributing to the improvement of women's capabilities and inclusion in the Finnish context.

In addition to the fundamental starting point, there have been no significant adjustments from the gender perspective during the piloting rounds.

Hungary

Gender-specific needs were not mentioned explicitly, but there are strong efforts to avoid gender bias in the TAIS design and make the process open and transparent throughout. Inclusion and diversity was considered during the design process with special attention to gender balance, ethnic diversity, and the inclusion of families – so that vulnerability can be seen from the children's perspectives as well. The selection of targeted HV individuals was subjected to the following criteria:

- The client was defined as HV according to the RAISD research,
- The client requested assistance in multiple situations (housing solution, schooling, health care, status administration, psychological assistance, access to social aid, etc.),
- He/she has been a client of Menedék for six months, and the social support lasted a minimum of 3 months,
- The client was living in Hungary.

Also, in Hungary, the general social work sector is characterised by mainly female service providers. This phenomenon is especially relevant for refugee-specific NGOs. However, we made efforts to include male representatives of organisations in the ARU and service providers as the beneficiaries of TAIS.

Turkey

Although the main target audience of TAIS is women and girls, the activities carried out in the TAIS process cover a more diverse target audience, considering the fact that some challenges women and girls face during their access to daily life practices are also experienced by many other social groups. This situation eventually increased the comprehensiveness and effectiveness of the development of the capacity of service providers to monitor service quality on the specific needs and challenges which can be considered as the major outcome of the TAIS. For this reason, gender perspective was taken into account while establishing the ARU and during the process of including new members to the research unit. In addition, local service providers and social workers who work with women, girls, LGBTIQ+ members and disabled individuals were also included in the trainings and discussions to ensure a comprehensive and diverse framework for the discussions regarding challenges in accessing daily life practices. On the other hand, the content of the trainings (inclusion, diversity and monitoring) mainly gather around the idea of diversity and inclusion which intensely focuses on the gender perspective.

In terms of gender equality, in the Turkish TAIS trainings, the ratio was 80% women, 20% male among the municipality social service workers. Because our target group was vulnerable women -especially Syrian and Iraqi women who have the highest vulnerability- men in the host community and FDP could not reach the trainings. However, throughout this project, we reached the men in the municipality too. In that way, we balanced our target group in terms of gender.

Jordan

Gender equity was incorporated into the design of TAIS. After the pilot training, some recommendations were developed to the implementers of the training pilots in order to support the learning process so as to increase the impact of the courses on the quality of the participants' psychosocial support services or related activities. Also, evaluation tools were developed with the purpose of continuous use by the pilot coordinators at both university and NGOs for future impact evaluations. Moreover, the evaluation aided us to measure the scale of psychological empowerment of women, gender norm attitudes scale, household decision-making scale, and developed skills after attending the training, which in turn would reflect on creating some social behaviour changes for the direct and the indirect participants accordingly.

Lebanon

In Lebanon, importance was given both to the research and structural aspects of gender in the TAIS process.

- Collecting the survey, it was around 60 % female and 40 % male participants during the 25 interviews of vulnerable people.
- The composition of the ARU meeting participants in LIU was balanced, with 60% of females and 40 % of males.

Collectively, the project embraced leadership between both men and women, despite the fact that the female counterparts in the core team outscored men. Both in the TAIS and the core RAISD team, the presence of several gender experts was noted.

4 From re-design to practice

4.1 *Benefits and difficulties of the Action Research methodology*

AR approach was of vital importance for an adequate adjustment of the TAIS programs to the changing context and the beneficiaries' needs and knowledge gaps. The AR strategy consists of alternating cycles of research/ evaluation with cycles of action, and it was this approach that enabled the project to tailor the TAIS program and make it suitable for the participants. This flexibility and proactive approach of the methodology was a key element that permitted answering and adjusting to new needs and changing contexts of the beneficiaries, something that was mentioned by most of the partners as the main benefit of AR. Navigating through stormy waters during the Covid-19 was in a great deal possible because of the flexibility of the TAIS programming. In terms of difficulties, partners mentioned that the lockdown measures and social distance caused by Covid-19 added a challenge to the application of AR, usually applied in real life situations and interactions, not online. Not included in the country reports, but often mentioned in informal conversations among the TAIS training providers in Spain, is the fact that reiterative research and innovation paths such as the ones we used for the TAIS, are time consuming and require great human resource efforts.

Spain

This flexible and proactive methodology, aligned not only with AR, but also with the RRI philosophy, helped the team to detect additional needs of training and gaps in the knowledge of some participants, such as extra Spanish language courses, IT skills training or personalised learning of business plan design. Right at the beginning of the first cycle of training in Spain, during summer 2020, the need for improving the beneficiaries' Spanish language skills became urgent, in quest of preparing the participants for the forthcoming professional and academic content. Also, training in gender, rights and empowerment sessions were included to raise the participants' general level of knowledge. Major changes to the training focus were made after each of the evaluation rounds, such as augmenting IT, accounts and business planning-related contents, but minor changes were made on the run, on a weekly basis. This flexibility and proactivity, adding and readjusting contents on the progress was the main benefit of AR to the Spanish TAIS, as it permitted a better embedding of the program in the beneficiaries' needs, requirements and preferences.

On the other hand, we must not forget the consequences of the pandemic at an economic, health, social and personal level for the organisations, people of the ARU and, especially, the beneficiary women in situations of special vulnerability. Furthermore, it was a completely unexpected circumstance at the time of the design of the RAISD project and the beginning of its implementation, coinciding with the design of the TAIS. Undoubtedly, adapting RAISD to the context of the pandemic would have been much more difficult without the clear advantage of the flexibility and adaptability of AR. At a time when, globally, organisations that work with migrants and refugees claimed to be working in the middle of the unknown, AR, as well as RRI, is clearly a methodological advantage.

Italy

The Italian ARU implemented a participatory AR approach throughout the different and complex project phases: first to study the most VGs and their VCs, meaning that diverse stakeholders were included in the process and asked about successful and to-avoid integration and inclusion policies and practices with FDP and hereby provided a set of actor-oriented criteria, standards and recommendations that should be adopted when designing tailored action strategies.

By contributing to the identification of several valuable TAIS ideas, then evaluated against the set of criteria through a first benchmarking exercise, the stakeholders filtered out the final TAIS (i.e. the AUCL) core concepts and needed elements for a successful inclusion strategy that would meet HVG's needs and comply with the organisational capacities of all actors involved.

Later on, the adoption of the AR methodology allowed also for a responsive adjustment to real-life conditions of the participants, during Covid-19 outbreaks, with the main benefit being the adjustments in the recruitment strategy that ultimately allowed it to implement the full range of activities.

Once all foreseen activities were finalised with GROUP 2 (training for African women at women's shelter of Cooperativa Nuova Generazione), a further stakeholder consultation occurred for the final benchmarking exercise and to gather feedback through testimonials (see Italian ARU Research Stories 1 and 2 in D7.1 [Research stories from the ARUs, https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/](https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/)).

Participation of Italian ARU stakeholders was motivated by clear, smart and long-term cooperation objectives, therefore embedding the AR approach into the AUCL strategy:

- To set and sustain a common quality framework for Learning and Training Environments (LTE) tailored for any highly vulnerable target groups profile;
- To enable quality assurance mechanisms and further improve learning-teaching environments for HVG;
- To monitor and evaluate critical points of implementation cycles;
- To support mutual trust and facilitate recognition and stakeholders' long-term cooperation, building a safe community around the highly vulnerable target groups along the inclusion process.

Finland

AR in the form that it is often described in method textbooks, is a difficult thing to accomplish during Pandemic and various lockdown measures and social distancing. There are few cases of plain online AR endeavours.

For those reasons, it is difficult to claim that the development of an online forum (TAIS I) has been conducted through AR from the start to the end. Obviously, the starting point of the whole project has been involvement in the everyday lives of both asylum seekers and the field of the reception system. Before the pandemic, this stance helped to see the needs and potential measures to be taken during the first year of the project. However, while developing the TAIS, there have been few chances to resort to AR in its traditional sense. In addition to asking feedback from the participants and recruiters, the aim has been to engage also in private discussions with those asylum seekers who

express their need of help in various issues. During and between the pilot rounds, there have been some exchanges of ideas with some asylum seekers.

In the TAIS II, the original plan was to be more engaged and physically present in the child-care services of the reception centre, but due to the pandemic, it was not possible. However, there were chances to resort to AR: asylum-seekers and professionals were interviewed and the TAIS methods included participatory observation in the reception centres in the second and third rounds. Through these methods, quantitative and qualitative feedback was collected. Moreover, improvements to the services and especially the trial of more intensive child-care were designed in close co-operation with professionals. Thus, due to adjustment related to the pandemic, the TAIS succeeded better in involving the professionals, while remote involvement of asylum-seeking parents was more difficult.

Hungary

The TAIS has been tailored to fit the needs of the Hungarian NGO and/or local governance context. Care practices are limited due to the harsh conditions of the local political environment, and pro-refugee organisations have taken the role of providing integration services. The Hungarian TAIS aims to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures: social workers and service providers in Budapest should be informed about who, where, and how to apply helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees.

The TAIS "Trajectory monitoring toolbox" for social workers and stakeholders (including ARU member institutions) contains, on the one hand, a Handbook in which the research results of VCs were transferred into training exercises, offering a practical task collection that processes the vulnerability of refugees living in Hungary along with current, real-life situations. On the other hand, a Self-reflection tool was developed that contains the results of the new pilot program in which the social workers and ARUs were involved to address the lack of reflexivity in the daily practices of service providers.

Every cycle of TAIS implementation had an evaluation and feedback process that involved ARU members. Based on the trajectories in real-life situations of TAIS Round 1, TAIS Round 2 aimed at enhancing organisational capacities through training and by incorporating existing knowledge in the daily operation of the given organisations. Based on case analyses and stakeholder inputs, the toolbox was finalised in the TAIS Round 3.

Turkey

ARU discussions were held regularly throughout the implementation process of TAIS including the planning, pilots and in between each training to ensure that the implementation is being adjusted to the specific needs of FDP. New members from different fields were included in the ARU to better respond to the needs and expectations of FDP. Furthermore, the need for the TAIS arose fully from the beneficiary interviews of those FDP. As being the main source of the TAIS concept, FDP actively took part in the TAIS design process, responding to the expectations expressed by this collective in the previous interviews. All ARU members, including research, education, civil society organisations & citizens, policy makers and businesses took part in the design of the TAIS.

Considering the RRI perspective, the representatives who received the training and who were also in the ARU during the TAIS process were both informed of the studies and findings within the scope of RAISD and used these research results to make the necessary revisions, arrangements and improvements in their own organisations and institutions.

Jordan

AR methodology improved the Jordanian TAIS and the efficiency of implemented services to meet the needs and demands of FDPs. It also allowed the team and ARUs to recognize a few ineffective methods through the implementation process and they were modified to fit the implementation and the target group. In this way, AR aided participants in improving the effectiveness of training designs and processes and the trainers' efficiency in imparting knowledge, development, and psychological support to the target group. The AR methodology also had the benefit of developing the problem-solving skills of the trainers and participants within and without the correct means for the service.

The incorporation of the critical evaluation of training design, analysis, and reflection results in the ability of the target group to find means to solve problems. It also enabled the implementers to sharpen the reasoning abilities of the target group and aided them in the development of measures of self-monitoring to augment performance effectiveness. Through AR, ARUs became more aware of their training design and practices, the difference between practice and beliefs, thoughts, feelings, and learning of the FDPs. This allows them to tailor their designs in a well-defined and effective way to meet the needs of FDPs. AR also aided in the ability of TAIS to focus on FDP explanations and conceptions. This is brought about by the fact that AR involves collecting data on target groups' understanding and thinking to act considering them.

Lebanon

At the start of the first cycle of training at LIU, from April 2020 to July 200, it was apparent English language was fundamental to improve the students' skills. Moreover, training which empowered the use of digital mobile and communication and leadership skills was very instrumental to fill the gaps of the target group. These adaptations, made independently of the content, were the result of the use of the AR methodology in the context of the Lebanese TAIS. This was considered to be a key benefit of the LIU TAIS, as it fostered a smooth adoption of the formation by the target group.

4.2 Changing designs and execution processes after TAIS evaluation rounds

The TAIS design process and first pilot and evaluation rounds are included in the previous deliverable D3.3., whereas D3.4 takes it from there, starting with the second TAIS round, it describes the necessary adjustments and changes made to the initial TAIS paths and execution plans. This chapter provides the readers insights into the practical aspects of the TAIS and their evolution, and examples of what kind of changes were needed after each evaluation round. These serve as examples of how to put in practice one of the RRI dimensions that gained especial relevance along the process, namely adaptive change (Stilgoe et al., 2012), that means the system's capacity of modifying ways of thinking and action as well as organisational structures in response to changing circumstances, being flexible in the face of new knowledge and diversity of perspectives. TAIS changes were in many cases foreseen changes, feasible

second options when the initial ones did not work properly, the kind of aspects we need to bear in mind when working in real social settings, where contextual factors and individual conditions of the beneficiaries constantly change. Often, the actual person-to-person contact and continuous collaboration with FDP and other beneficiary groups (such as the social workers or the organisations) raised the level of confidence and trust among TAIS participants, facilitators and trainers, helping beneficiaries to come clean and express their needs and claims.

Spain

The evaluation processes of the first and second rounds evidenced the need to make content adjustments in the training sessions.

Throughout the first round, the first change was the methodology for their delivery, which, due to the Covid-19 context (macro level with consequences on meso and micro levels), had to be adapted to the online modality. In addition to the incorporation of specific content for the acquisition of digital skills, the provision of material means that would allow the beneficiaries to participate in the training was necessary. During this first round of TAIS, the incorporation of a social worker profile was necessary to ensure that the beneficiaries were able to handle electronic devices, access the sessions and master the online work tools used.

The weekly evaluations by the trainers made it possible to reinforce certain contents to ensure the correct progress of the beneficiaries (micro level).

During the second round, health security conditions (macro level with consequences on meso and micro levels) could be ensured to resume the face-to-face modality. A profile of a social worker was maintained as a link with the project, reinforcing teamwork and ensuring that the beneficiaries had all the necessary resources to attend the sessions in a safe environment for their health (masks, hydroalcoholic gel, public transport tickets, health information) (micro level). This key figure was also a point of contact with the entities that serve these beneficiaries, generating synergies and helping us to better understand their context (meso level).

Additionally, there were two profiles of trainers directly related to entrepreneurship that were added to the TAIS after the second round: a company and a non-profit organisation specialised in the employability of migrants. These two organisations based the content design on the business idea identified by the beneficiaries (meso level).

Spanish TAIS coordinators were in charge of incorporating training sessions to reinforce the aspects worked on by these two organisations, adapting the reinforcements based on the weekly evaluations. In this way, the team ensured the achievement of the proposed learning objectives, at the pace that the beneficiaries needed (micro and meso levels).

Finally, new specific collaborators were contacted to work specifically in the areas of economics (lecturers from other universities), suppliers and professionals related to the business idea selected by the beneficiaries, attendance at social entrepreneurship events aimed at migrants, as well as inspirational examples about similar businesses (micro and meso levels).

Italy

The [AUCL concept and design](#) were not altered at its core between the piloting rounds and groups. The execution though underwent consistent changes in lengths, intensity and implementation venue. The Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis after the piloting with Group 1 (October/December 2020) led to a higher awareness on strengths and weaknesses of the TAIS initial design and its methodology, which resulted in the development of a responsive Actionable Strategy: a change in the participants' recruitment model. Differently from the first piloting round, where women were invited to participate by their women day care centres of reference, for the second piloting group (May/September 2021) it was then CESIE's trainers to visit the CAS centres to deliver the training course. This surely inhibited participants' experiencing their ability to orient themselves autonomously in the local inclusion process and services during the training activities, but ensured continuity to the participants.

Methods and activities had to be adjusted and reduced in time and intensity. The level of interaction between the HVG and the hosting community was consistently limited.

The Italian TAIS worked with two types of piloting groups: Western African (mainly from Nigeria) and Eastern African (majority from Somalia) migrants, mainly women. The TAIS design was largely based on the differences and commonalities between the two diverse HVG piloting groups at micro-level as well as for the meso-level that considers the organisational aspects.

Finland

All the changes or modifications to the online forum took place on an individual level. Modifications aimed to improve the TAIS in order to suit better mainly the needs and hopes of asylum seekers. Changes were based on process evaluation of the first and second cycles and included things such as simpler communication, including peer moderators, training volunteers and peer moderators and focusing on discussion topics with more concrete contents. Moreover, after the first and second pilot rounds, a discussion with a Red Cross coordinator took place to share the evaluation results.

Instead of inventing completely new services, already existing services were developed in the TAIS II. Therefore, the process started by evaluating the current child-care services in reception centres. The first round was about creating a comprehensive picture of the services in all reception centres of the Finnish Red Cross (FRC). The second round was to deepen the qualitative knowledge of child-care services in the two involved reception centres of the FRC and to gain a more thorough understanding of the material, cultural and social conditions of the services to benchmark the best practices and to improve the content of the services. The outcomes of these evaluation rounds were communicated to the reception centre professionals to be utilised in improving the quality and the contents of the services. Based on feedback collected in the first and second round, the main problem in the current services was the insufficient amount of child-care. Therefore, the third round was a trial of more intensive child-care.

Hungary

In Hungary, evaluation of TAIS round 1 took place in November 2020. Social workers at Menedék could skillfully describe the history of complex case management of their HV clients in the form of a case study. These case studies could be used as a primary source for the creation of vulnerability profiles.

Adding further perspectives to the analyses was nonetheless necessary, as the key idea of the TAIS was to ensure multi-perspective approaches to cases of vulnerability. Further professionals who joined the description of vulnerable individuals' case processes could do so using a methodology similar to that of the initial social workers. The activities related to this pillar started from the second half of September 2020.

The first evaluation and cross analysis could, therefore, detect the importance of the multi-perspective approach which was fed back to the initial idea of developing the skills of social workers through trainings based on real-life situations and client profiles.

The second evaluation of the Hungarian TAIS was in April 2021. In Round 2, the inputs from case descriptions were organised into work plans for developing organisational capacities through trainings and by incorporating the gathered knowledge in the daily work of social workers. Feedback from the lessons learnt in Round 1 was guiding the main activities in the Hungarian TAIS. However, the piloting of the self-reflection appeared to be challenging: in April 2021 the methodology of self-reflection was revised and tailored to the practical aspects of working with refugees at an NGO which, contrary to larger service providers, has limited human resources and no control over administrative processes that shape the reality of vulnerable refugees.

Finally, the third evaluation was carried out in November 2021. Following the success of the draft version of the handbook in ARU meetings held throughout the third round, the draft was further developed, revisited and then finalised. The piloting process of the self-reflection program was evaluated and altered according to the feedback received from the social workers. Drafting of the self-reflection study about the results of the program has started, was revisited and then finalised. All these elements were evaluated from an end-of-process perspective in October 2021 with the help of the ARU.

A final element was planned to be added to the TAIS, namely, a multi-day workshop fostering inter-organizational cooperation among stakeholders working with refugees. Given the security concerns related to the COVID-19 pandemic, this element was not implemented. Further ARU meetings in 2022 will serve as a platform for the activities planned as part of the TAIS.

Turkey

In the Turkish TAIS design, there were no changes in content, which were built on the insights from the ARU and FDP interviews. There has been a change in the TAIS format. The trainings were planned to be held face-to-face, although the participants physically attended the trainings, the trainers participated online via Zoom. As a result of the evaluations, it was concluded that the trainings and experiences could be transferred not only directly to the VGs themselves, but also to the local governments working with the VGs as well. As a result of the TAIS process, municipal

employees also agreed that they could incorporate these training courses into their work processes. At the meso level, the project created a perceptual shift in the municipality's mentality: the institution needed to change and put in practice the new capacities and adapt learning outcomes to the daily practices.

Jordan

There were changes conducted to assess the relevance and project design components and interventions and its linkage to the overall goal and specific objectives of the project. The validity of the training program with its five sub-programs (Psychosocial Empowerment, Health Empowerment, Economic Empowerment, Legal Empowerment, and Family Empowerment) was verified by presenting it to a group of (58) specialists, university professors and experts, specialised in preparing training programs in health, psychological, economic, family and legal fields. They determined the program's suitability and concluded that some amendments should be considered to meet the program objectives. The amendments include a number of procedures and exercises that deal with related topics. Adjustments on the program's time period were made in order to make it flexible and suit the trainer and the training purposes. Emotional relief exercises were added to ensure that the training days end in an emotionally safe manner. Some activities and exercises were reviewed and re-structured in order to improve the designs.

The identification of psychological resilience, the possibility of measurement, and the psychological goals targeting refugees were also taken into consideration while modifying the training designs. A pilot training in health empowerment was held in order to try the effectiveness of the training. Using pre and post surveys helped in identifying and measuring the effectiveness of the pilot training and modifications were conducted accordingly.

Lebanon

During the course of the first round, and due to the problems affecting Lebanon, it became inevitable to deliver the modules online. Moreover, the integration of digital skills and media in the course curricula meant that the facilitation of such material would allow the beneficiaries to better participate in the training.

LIU was able to successfully guarantee that the attainment of the proposed learning objectives was reached at the appropriate pace for the beneficiaries.

4.3 Unexpected local events motivating change in the TAIS execution

Apart from the unexpected Covid-19 outbreak consequences to the TAIS all over (as described in D5.3), most of the participating countries experienced unexpected events that motivated changes at national level, often with indirect effects on the TAIS designs and contents or the climate and attitudes towards FDP. With the exception of Hungary and Finland, which reported no significant changes in the local context, unexpected events were especially adverse in Lebanon, and relevant changes were also experienced in Italy, in this case positive, and in Spain, Turkey, Jordan, where these were negative. In Spain, the worsened economic situation and rising voices of openly xenophobic parties contributed to critical attitudes towards migrants, and even if the country received less FDP during the pandemics, there was a bottleneck in the asylum-seeking system. In Italy, the new decree on migration and security offered significant changes (at least on paper) on the FDP acceptance to the second reception system as well as the type and

level of services provided in the accommodation facilities. In Turkey, the economic crisis generated more negative perceptions on FDP among the host communities and the general climate of opinion generated even suspicions on the legitimacy and aims of the TAIS (as it was thought state led by some publics). In Jordan, the political and economic instability required the design of crisis management plans at Yarmouk University, whereas Lebanon faced the most acute difficulties: the political appraisal and riots starting in autumn 2019, with the economic crisis worsening with the Beirut port explosion in August 2020 and the consequent political, social and economic difficulties.

Spain

The decline of economic stability and worsened work market perspectives as a result of the pandemics had a negative impact on people's expectations and optimism, and FDP were among the most affected. Also, as often happens during a crisis, xenophobia and hate speech augmented their presence, even in some legally established political parties, contributing to a growing number of highly mediatic cases of violence against migrants, causing insecurity among FDP residing in Spain. These elements together with the forced social isolation during the pandemic might have contributed to the TAIS participants' general level of motivation and optimism. For this reason, as soon as the health situation allowed it, face-to-face and outdoor activities were carried out to improve the motivation of the participants. Also, during the past 2 years, migration policies have not improved or considerably facilitated the legal process for acquiring refugee status, quite the contrary, the process has become slower and experienced bottlenecks in the past year. Hence, in our TAIS, more motivational work and contents needed to be included in the course curricula, such as successful migrants' testimonies, gender empowering, self-knowledge and rights.

Italy

Considering that the piloting with Group 2 was implemented inside a CAS centre, it is of interest to know about the latest legislative developments, since in October 2020 a new decree on migration and security came into force, which modified some of the provisions introduced by the so-called "Salvini Security Decrees" in 2018 and 2019.

The accommodation system (former System of Protection for Refugees and Asylum Seekers (*Sistema di protezione per richiedenti asilo e rifugiati*, SPRAR) into the System of Protection for Beneficiaries of Protection and Unaccompanied Minors (*Sistema di protezione per titolari di protezione internazionale e minori stranieri non accompagnati*, SIPROIMI)¹.) is now called System of Accommodation and Integration (SAI).

Decree Law 130/2020 converted into Law 173/2020 has significantly changed – at least in theory – two fundamental aspects of the reception system for asylum seekers:

- Access to the (second) reception system;
- Type and level of services provided in first and second accommodation facilities.

¹ Evolution of the NATIONAL ASYLUM PROGRAMME:

- I. 2001 PNA – Programma Nazionale Asilo: the first public system for the reception of asylum seekers and refugees, throughout the Italian territory and instituted the sharing of responsibilities between the Ministry of the Interior and local authorities.
- II. 2002 SPRAR – Sistema di protezione per richiedenti asilo e rifugiati (Protection System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees)
- III. 2018 SIPROIMI – Sistema di protezione per titolari di protezione internazionale e per minori stranieri non accompagnati (Protection System for Beneficiaries of International Protection and for Unaccompanied Foreign Minors)

In case of unavailability of places due to a large influx of arrivals, first reception may be implemented in “temporary structures” (strutture temporanee), also known as Emergency Reception Centres (Centri di accoglienza straordinaria, CAS), established by Prefectures, subject to an assessment of the applicant’s health conditions and potential special needs. When reception is provided in CAS, it is limited to the time strictly necessary for the transfer of the applicant in the second reception centres.

Under the validity of the Legislative decree 142/2015, the effective access to second reception facilities for asylum seekers was often illusory. The extraordinary centres, CAS, whose activation was – and is – ordered by the Prefectures in case of lack of places in the ordinary system, represented – and represents – over the 70% of the facilities where asylum seekers were and are accommodated. Only a small number of asylum seekers were able to access the second reception system whose projects were – and are – voluntarily joined by the municipalities and whose places from 2011 onwards have always been seriously insufficient to cover the reception needs.

The other important aspect affected by Decree Law 130/2020 is the type of services that asylum seekers can benefit from. In theory the following services should be provided: social and psychological assistance, cultural mediation, Italian language courses, legal information service and information on territorial services. They are all services that the 2018 tender specification schemes had cancelled.

However, the picture that emerges from the new tender specification schemes published on 24 February 2021 on the Ministry of the Interior (Italy) (Moi) website is not at all comforting. The services that with the previous specifications and regulatory framework had been zeroed are now effectively provided for and included in the accountable costs but the expected increase in costs for these services and above all the hourly amounts of the respective operators are so low that the forecast appears to be only a formula without content. That is, the specification reveals how the actual interest in having these services actually implemented in first reception is in fact scarce null and void.

This is extremely relevant considering that, de facto, asylum seekers spend all the time of the asylum procedure or most of it in the first reception centres or in CAS.

On paper, the same level of services is provided for asylum seekers who will access to the SAI before the recognition of an international or special protection: here asylum seekers will be able to benefit from “first level” services which do not include support for integration, job research, job orientation and professional training, limited to beneficiaries of international and special protection.

However, in practice, due to the low level of services provided for the first accommodation facilities, there will be a significant difference between those who will live in SAI and those who will be accommodated in CAS or first reception facilities.

Only unaccompanied children have immediate access to SAI. It is confirmed that local authorities can also accommodate in SAI victims of trafficking; domestic violence and particular exploitation; persons issued a residence permit for medical treatment, or natural calamity in the country of origin, or for acts of particular civic value. Moreover, Decree Law 130/2020 states that local authorities can also accommodate in these facilities asylum

seekers, holders of special protection, holders of special cases protection (former humanitarian protection), and adults, former unaccompanied minors, who obtained a prosecution of assistance. Holders of special protection, in case of application of the international protection exclusion clauses, are excluded from the SAI.

More about “Policies, laws and treaties affecting attention and inclusion strategies towards VGs of FDP, in Italy” by CESIE, July 2020. (Retrieved from <https://raisd-h2020.eu/media/d5.1-potential-gps-it.pdf>).

Finland and Hungary

During the TAIS implementation process no unexpected events happened (other than Covid-19).

Turkey

The biggest problems experienced in TAIS pilot trainings were delays, rescheduling and inability to hold face-to-face meetings due to Covid-19. Participants were attending the meetings in person whereas trainers participated mainly via zoom because they were from different cities. The problems experienced outside of Covid-19, are the economic problems experienced in Turkey, as emphasised by the participants. The economic difficulties experienced in Turkey have caused the host community to have a more negative view of the FDP. Although this situation did not technically change the course of the project, a more moderate and motivating attitude was developed for the participants who benefited from the project team and trainers. This also strengthened the need to bridge the FDP of the ARU members and the social workers who are the beneficiaries of the project.

In addition, before and during the training, including Anadolu University ARU members, no one wanted to share their identity, including the social workers of Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality, who participated in the training. This is because the issue of FDP in Turkey is a sensitive issue. People are hesitant to talk about it because it is unclear to them what the consequences might be.

Another unexpected problem stood out was that some participants suspected that this project was carried out specifically for the state of the Republic of Turkey. People think such projects are produced by the higher authorities as a way of forcing the host community to accept the FDP. It showed us again that the host community, and more importantly for this project, even some social workers who work with FDP have prejudices towards refugees in Turkey.

Jordan

One of the things that could be necessary to face unexpected events in the country is to follow the YU-TAIS methodology to design training for risk and crisis management. This is due to the political and economic instability the region has gone and still goes through.

Lebanon

It is very difficult to split Covid-19 from other crises in Lebanon and the problems and delays it represented in efforts made to implement the TAIS study. Lebanon was already going through extraordinarily difficult political, social and

economic crises that were exacerbated further by the catastrophic Beirut Port explosion which caused 218 deaths, injured over 6,500 and made 300,000 homeless. This constituted an unforeseen risk factor that was to impact the direction of the study and the adjustments that were made to move the research process forward.

In the aftermath of the Beirut disaster, the government resigned due to its failures in preventing the explosion, protecting people, and responding with proper relief actions and policies. Lebanon later declared a state of emergency and granted the national Army expanded power and jurisdiction. As a consequence, a series of lockdowns and curfews were put in place to control the spread of the virus. The effects of these measures were devastating, with many closing shops, and citizens experiencing income cuts and job losses.

4.4 Need for new types of collaborators as the TAIS programs advance

In the running of the TAIS, new needs were discovered both in the formal evaluation rounds and in the immediate feedback on the daily activities of the TAIS, justifying the recruitment of new kinds of professional profiles. In Spain, the quest for a social worker became a bondage element for the relationship between trainers and beneficiaries, and to give extra support to the learners, especially for the most unprivileged ones. Another key figure in the Spanish TAIS were the mentors, and such was the case also in Italy, where mentors were engaged to give practical assistance, serve as role models and help course beneficiaries to find their own paths and to improve their self-confidence. In Finland, municipal officials and workers responsible for municipal day-care services were interviewed to know the root causes for the lack of this kind of services. In the migrant online forum, instead of recruiting new professionals, FDP were asked to adopt a new role and have a more active performance to foster other migrants' participation. In Turkey, new trainer profiles were included along the TAIS process, among others scholars in the field of Social Sciences and experts with experience in working with VGs. In Hungary, direct participants were social workers and assisting professionals of relevant institutions and organisations, but during the process, the profile was expanded and both municipal and state officials were invited to participate in the ARU. In Jordan, a need for evaluator profiles arose during the TAIS rounds II and III and also, experts in the 5 key knowledge areas were engaged in the program. In Lebanon, health specialists were involved in the TAIS program due to the outbreak of Covid-19.

Spain

After the evaluation of the first round of TAIS, a social worker was recruited to provide technical support with the beneficiaries during the transition from training to online mode.

During the second cycle of TAIS, the social worker focused on the detection of weekly needs, mainly to reinforce group belonging and cohesion and to serve as connection to the project coordinators, as well as to improve the coordination with the ARU member entities that were contributing to the sessions.

A company with experience in entrepreneurship with online pedagogical methodology, PAZ.ai, as well as the NGO Nantik Lum had a very active participation and gave most of the lectures during the second and third round of the TAIS, helping the initiative to meet the learning objectives.

As soon as the restrictions caused by Covid-19 ended and face-to-face activity was recovered, the social worker became crucial to implementation of the new modality. In addition, she coordinated most of the practical activities, such as face-to-face visits to suppliers, as well as formal consultations related to the potential start of economic activity within the administrations of the Community of Madrid.

Also, other ARU members collaborated transversally in the second and third round of the TAIS, providing the beneficiaries opportunities to assist events related to social entrepreneurship for migrants, such as the Ashoka Global Summit.

Finally, the Spanish TAIS benefitted from the support of experts for a number of training sessions: university lecturers, economists, business women, entrepreneurs and volunteers who have helped to reinforce knowledge gaps or new needs detected in the weekly evaluations.

Italy

The [ALL you can LEARN \(AUCL\) concept and design](#) were not altered at its core between the piloting rounds and groups. The execution though underwent consistent changes in location, lengths, intensity and actors involved due to the Covid-19 restrictions.

In terms of types of collaborators, the main profile that was brought in was that of a mentor.

Thus, the first piloting round included the professional mentors' profile to foster own community engagement as identified as a Standard for potential Good Practices (see [D5.1 Italy\Standard 10 pag.22](#)). The referred Principle is that migrants or people from ethnic minorities often do not have any role models in future oriented fields throughout their job careers or health conditions, neither within their families nor in their social contexts. Therefore, it is considered crucial to offer HVFDP support figures from their own ethnic communities who accompany them on their way to a successful autonomy.

The matching process enables shared language and culture and similar experiences to strengthen the mentoring relationships and the mentor's ability to empathise and understand the experiences of the young mentee, and the mentee to have someone to identify with. Moreover, it is important to consider the different perceptions of one's own body or that of others. The perception and the concept of pain and disease can vary according to individual biographical and cultural variables.

Therefore, the AUCL Mentors were assigned several tasks and responsibilities, among others: to ensure individual and ongoing mentoring support for each of the 5 mentees assigned; to collaborate with the training experts in the implementation of the educational project; to accompany and support (physical accompaniment, where/when necessary) the participants during educational activities on the days, hours and locations defined by the Training calendar (scheduled were 20h orientation and group building / 40h face-to-face training / 20h study visits on the territory / 10h evaluation and usability of the results); to help in the choice and support the understanding of the [modules' MENU](#) selection procedure (with each of the participants assigned). They were also asked: to fill in the Mentoring Diary for each of the 5 participants (ensure that the attendance and signatures of the participants, experts

and their own, are reported in the attendance register); to overview the completion of the registration forms and signing the Learners' Agreement; to take care of the attendance monitoring of the course, reporting in real time and contacting the students in case of unjustified absence; to cooperate with the experts who carry out monitoring or budgeting actions, ensuring that the intervention is carried out with responsibility and motivation. Within their commitments, they also maintained contact with the training manager to monitor the inclusion outcomes of the inclusion intervention, delivered a final evaluation report on the tutoring activities carried out and participated in shared meetings with other mentors and trainers.

The second pilot round was ultimately implemented with and at CAS "Cooperativa Nuova Generazione" in the nearby town of Trabia (20 km distance from Palermo). Here the role of the AUCL Mentors was taken over by the CAS's own multidisciplinary team: coordinator, educators, legal operator, psychologist, mediator.

Finland

There was no need for completely new collaborators to carry out the latest rounds of TAIS. However, there has been a need to invite some of the asylum seekers to adopt new types of roles in the forum. This has meant engaging them as peer moderators instead of only participants. This has encouraged them to be more active in the forum and help other participants to express their ideas in different languages.

The main principle in the Finnish sub-project has been the involvement of key stakeholders in the process of designing the TAIS, referring particularly to asylum seekers and reception centre professionals. Since the Finnish reception system is a highly segregated institution, legislatively and administratively isolated from other public bodies and societal sectors, the inclusion of stakeholders such as municipal authorities, several NGOs and private companies has been somewhat difficult.

However, in the second round of TAIS II, the public sector was involved as a new type of collaborator. Based on the interviews carried out in the first round, a key aspiration of the asylum-seeking parents was to get their children into municipal day-care centres. Moreover, the information gathering in the first round showed municipalities applying very varying practices in asylum seekers' access to day-care services. Therefore, municipal officials and workers responsible for municipal day-care services were interviewed to discover the roots of varying practices of municipalities.

Hungary

There were two participatory roles in the TAIS activities. The direct participants were social workers and assisting professionals of relevant institutions and organisations (including ARU members but also representatives of other institutions). The clients (vulnerable individuals) participate indirectly through the interviews they have given to describe their case studies.

The coordination and facilitation of the TAIS activities were conducted by Menedék as the central actor. The external promoters were represented by ARU members whose contribution was significant for good communication and practices.

Furthermore, over the project process, ARU member profiles have been expanded as we invited representatives from the municipality and state levels.

In the piloting phase, the range of colleagues involved in the self-reflection program has expanded. We have included all colleagues who provide assistance to refugees within Menedék. Also, the number of participants during the workshops and trainings have changed according to the interest of other organisations members.

Turkey

In the Turkish pre-pilot sessions there were 3 types of trainers; Turkish project coordinator, communication specialists and academicians. Prof. Dr. Erol Nezih Orhon – RAISD Anadolu University team project coordinator-, Dr. Duygu Tosunay Gencelli – expert on international communication and diplomacy communication, also an academician in the field of social sciences and communication science- and Dr. Çağlar Genç - an academician on communication sciences and expert on cultural diversity-. After this first phase, The Turkish TAIS main training activity included the following 3 profiles: communication expert Pınar Alkan from the United Nations, Emel Danişoğlu from the social service area and Dr. Özlem Boztaş from TED University. Pınar Alkan from the United Nations has worked on a large number of projects funded by the United Nations and European Union Delegation in Turkey. She provided a series of international policy and foreign municipality policy examples on working with vulnerable people. Emel Danişoğlu was from the social service field, well experienced in the field of social work. She has been working with vulnerable groups in the field and she is a social expert who also works with public authorities. She gave a speech and examples about how to reach people by serving them to get their rights and needs. She also talked about gender equality in social work. The last trainer was Dr. Özlem Boztaş from the academic field. She is specialised in gender and has experience as advisor and project executor in local municipalities' social projects. She also has expertise in rights- and needs-based issues and monitoring. She has been involved in several projects focusing on gender equality and antidiscrimination.

New members joined our ARU during the execution of TAIS training. Eskişehir Bar Association, which is an expert on accessing rights, is an example of that.

Jordan

After the first TAIS round, new collaborators were needed in order to play a great part in the efficiency and success of the TAIS. The first step was presenting to collaborators the needs of refugees in terms of enhanced inclusion in the host community and assistance in five areas (legal, health, economic, psychological support, and family empowerment). For the II and III TAIS rounds and their evaluation, an assessment collaborator was needed to measure and analyse the validity of the training programs. The team also utilised the expertise of 58 specialists, university professors and experts, specialised in preparing training programs in the mentioned fields. Their feedback was helpful in adjusting some activities and practices within the training design to assure the efficiency of the training programs. Trainers who were part of the national and international ARU members were needed to implement the training programs. Each specialist trainer engaged with the related topic and had an understanding of what the TAIS were trying to achieve in order to ascertain the success and efficiency of the training materials. This was measured

by evaluating the participants' willingness to continue with the training and the questions-answer responses between the trainers and the participants.

Lebanon

Upon the evaluation of the first round of TAIS between April 13 - 20, 2020, immediate action to form a Health committee was developed. In addition, an online committee was formed to help adaptation to the needs that arose during the pandemic.

During the course, digital mobile was a must for students to be trained, as computers were not available for students. This difficulty was shared with ARU members who have been very collaborative and supportive.

4.5 Information flows of the TAIS process and services

Communication plays an important role in the TAIS strategy and forms part of the RAISD transparent communication management, furthermore, it was vital for spreading the word and making all the TAIS phases public and available for the interested key stakeholders, especially to organisations (NGOs, international humanitarian aid agencies, reception centres, administrative bodies, academic institutions) that could collaborate in the training sessions and inform those FDP that could become program beneficiaries. The current chapter details the core communication activities taken by the partners, with the collaboration of the ARU members, to announce the TAIS and make them known, especially among organisations that work in the field giving direct assistance to FDP and those migrants under their service cover, eligible for the programs.

The aim of this chapter is to provide insights on the basic information flows and communication, necessary for the planning, running and operating of the tailored inclusion strategies. In communication studies, this kind of information flows and communication is often understood as semi-internal/semi-external, as it mainly reaches the inside stakeholders of a certain domain, the stakeholders that are highly involved in the subject, in our case, in the attention and inclusion of FDP. The broader external communication efforts related to the whole project, including the TAISs, are included in RAISD general outreach and dissemination strategy, which include numerous actions recollected in several WP9 deliverables, available upon request (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/process-oriented-results/>).

As explained in several TAIS-related reports, the ARUs established in the beginning of the project included stakeholders involved in forced migration study and assistance from the fields of research & education, civil society, policy makers, and even from business. NGOs, international humanitarian aid organisations and FDP themselves had a key role in all the phases of the project. Therefore, communicating and collaborating in the ARUs from the very beginning made the TAIS feasible, as the ARU members contributed in several aspects: they contributed to the design, execution and evaluation of the strategies; they helped to find the most needy beneficiaries; they acted as trainers/facilitators and they spread the word among their contacts.

In Spain, the information exchange and communication took place mostly in the 11 ARU meetings during the 3 years of the project, gathering together around 51 persons representing 35 organisations. These meetings were also disseminated in RAISD social media.

Also in Italy, the ARU members were a key public for the bilateral communication efforts, mostly CSOs and local administrative entities, among others Ikenga migrant association for socio-cultural promotion, Centro Astalli, Donne di Benin City - Human trafficking victims support centre and ASP provincial health care systems' ethno-psychology service. Italy also presented a paper on the TAIS in the [ICERI2021 -International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation](#) (November 7-8, 2021).

In Finland, FDP attention is mainly the competence of the FRC, so the TAIS were established in collaboration with this organisation, but communication and collaboration links were also established with the reception centres and public administration, including the Ministry of Education and Culture and municipality officers, apart from direct communication with FDP, especially during TAIS I, the online forum.

The Hungarian team reached out to the refugee-specific organisations and held several ARU meetings with a growing number of participants. Menedék also did active communication towards external publics via their social media and website, as well as distributing a newsletter about the TAIS results.

As in all the project countries, also in Turkey the communication about and around the TAIS was highly focused on the ARU members, they even used a shared Whatsapp group, and the team opened RAISD Anadolu University social media accounts for the project.

The Jordanian TAIS process was communicated to the existing ARU members, experts in education, law, health and economic fields, NGOs and other experts interested in providing psychological support, but it also had social media and national media channel coverage.

In Lebanon, several profiles of stakeholders were informed and participated in the research and design process for the TAIS. These included non-profits Tatwer Baladna (<https://www.tatweerbaldna.org/>) and Spark (<https://spark.ngo/>), UNRWA, researchers and an ex Minister of Foreign and Trade Affairs. A great deal of external communication was done by the social media channels.

How the relationship between the TAIS organising team and external stakeholders were established are detailed in D6.3 Report on the involvement of local stakeholders, and more specifics on the ARU collaborators can be found in D6.2 Report on the implementation of TAIS in the ARUS (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>).

In the following, the partner countries explain the key aspects of their TAIS information flows.

Spain

TAIS design and evaluation process was twofold, on one hand, including the work of 11 ARU meetings (up to March 2022) and on the other, the core team's and service providers direct conversations with each other and the beneficiaries.

In the first phases of ARU design, the most relevant NGOs and other civil society organisations, researchers, advanced students, companies (that had previous experience with migrants), national and local policymakers and several FDP (with whom the team had previous contacts) were mapped and then contacted to participate in the ARU meetings or workshops. All the Spanish core team members had previous work experience in projects related to FDP, so their personal networks were useful for the initial mapping of potential stakeholders and many of them were eager to participate in the project and join the ARU. Many of them got highly engaged with the project and participated in most of the workshops. The level of fidelity became high among ARU members. Also, word-of-mouth communication worked really well among the participants, as in case one could not come to a meeting, she/he would recommend a colleague. Some entities, due to an unexpected increase in workload, were unable to participate in the ARU meetings for a while, but they have decided to participate again, re-joining the ARU.

The ARU members participated throughout the whole process: the definition of the vulnerable groups in Spain, in selecting the beneficiary type, and in designing, evaluating and improving the TAIS program. Around 51 external people representing 35 organisations participated in the process, with an average of around 20 participants in each ARU meeting.

The beneficiaries were mainly located with the assistance of the NGOs that work with FDP, though the individual networks of the core team researchers were useful for this as well. Most of these organisations were active ARU members, so they learned about the program in the respective ARU meetings, but also, information brochures were sent via mail to NGOs working with FDP. The beneficiaries learned about the program via their respective assisting core organisations and especially, via the social workers in direct contact with African FD women.

All the engaged ARU participants were invited to the successive meetings and informed about the advances during the workshops and via short messages. The communication was mainly carried out by mail and phone. Video calls were also made with previous ARU members and new organisations that are experts in entrepreneurship or that work with migrant women of sub-Saharan origin to inform them of the project and the TAIS, as well as to offer them to join the ARU and the future observatory. Spanish ARU is always open and constantly growing, the XI ARU meeting, with the specific topic of policy recommendations, took place in December 2021 and yet, another meeting is foreseen during Spring 2022, to work on the project sustainability.

The external communication on each workshop core results and theme was released by social media posts in RAISD Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn accounts. In the same way, some activities and achievements of the TAIS program were shared through these social media accounts, as well as those of the collaborating organisations or service providers, thus increasing the number of people informed about the TAIS.

Finally, and considering the consortium as a whole, AB members have also been informed of our TAIS.

Italy

To thank and acknowledge all the stakeholders joining the Italian ARU and participating at the research process across the different TAIS design and developments stages, the Italian team has prepared a detailed list of all the stakeholders included in the information flows:

During the research phase, including needs analysis, vulnerability profiling, best practice identification and actor-oriented criteria definition, the following stakeholders were informed and involved:

- CSC Centro per lo Sviluppo Creativo 'Danilo Dolci', Palermo (Advisory Board, AB).
- IKENGA migrant association for socio-cultural promotion, Palermo (AB members).
- CLEDU Legal Clinic for Human Rights of the University of Palermo.
- ARCI Porco Rosso, Sportello Sans-Papiers, Palermo.
- CPIA Regional School Office for Sicily. Provincial Centre for Adult Education, Palermo.
- Istituto Don Calabria (Vulnerable group housing), Palermo.
- ASP Provincial Health Care System: Ethno-psychology Service, Palermo.
- Citizen, Voluntary legal guardian for unaccompanied minors, Palermo.
- INTEGRA Network (30+ regional members: connecting residential care providers, educators, successful care leavers, VET providers, educational institutions, local authorities working with migrants, guardians of unaccompanied minors), Sicily.

During Fieldwork, several organisations gave their support to carrying out the 25 HVG interviewees, among them Emergency Reception Centres like CasPa 4 San Francesco, Palermo; and entities such as Associazione Casa Famiglia Nostra Signora di Lourdes – Onlus (shelter home for disabled persons), Villafrati; Centro Astalli – Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS), Palermo and INTEGRA Network.

During Piloting GROUP1:

- Centro Astalli – Jesuit Refugee Service (voluntary association), Palermo.
- Il Pellegrino della Terra, Human Trafficking Victims support centre (civil society organisations), Palermo.
- Donne di Benin City – Human Trafficking Victims support centre, Palermo.
- Donne Islamiche Fatima, Palermo.
- IKENGA migrant association for socio-cultural promotion, Palermo [AB Board members].
- Centro PENC Anthropology and Geo Clinical Psychology, Palermo.
- INTEGRA Network
- CSC Centro per lo Sviluppo Creativo 'Danilo Dolci', Palermo [Advisory Board members].

During Piloting GROUP2:

- [CAS.A\Pilot partner] Cooperativa Nuova Generazione (CNG) (Progetto Freedom, CAS Musciotto), Trabia.
- [CAS.B] Società Cooperativa Sociale 3P | Padre Pino Puglisi, Palermo.
- [CAS.C] Consorzio "Umana Solidarietà s.c.s. (reception services for asylum seekers), Palermo.
- [Study visit] Moltivolti (Social Enterprise), Palermo.
- [Study visit] Associazione CU.CI.RE (Cooperative Union for Creative Ideas and Re-starting Entrepreneurship), Palermo.

- CSC Centro per lo Sviluppo Creativo 'Danilo Dolci', Palermo [Advisory Board members].
- ASP Provincial Health Care System: Ethno-psychology Service, Palermo.
- CPIA Regional School Office for Sicily. Provincial Centre for Adult Education, Palermo.

Besides the collaborations with the partners above, further dissemination and communication activities were implemented through different online channels, platforms and conferences:

- ARU/Competence Cell website section aimed at the following audience: researchers, project managers, politicians, social activists, citizens (<https://cesie.org/en/competence-cell/>).
- Official RAISD social media and reposted on CESIE's networks, with a large audience of FDP, migrants and refugees, NGOs, CSO, citizens, youth (<https://www.facebook.com/raisd.h2020/>).
- More Than a Job Portal, targeting public institutions in the field of employment and skills assessment, including ministries of labour, education, migration and related bodies; Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE) entities organisations active in the field of employment; unemployed people focusing on newly arrived migrants and refugees.
 - <https://www.enicbcmec.eu/projects/morethanajob>
 - <https://www.joinmorethanajob.org/collaboration/53> (AUCL)
 - The portal includes and integrated an offer of services for the well-being of the community
 - This portal is developed as part of the EU-funded ENI CBC MED project "MoreThanAJob – Reinforcing social and solidarity economy for the unemployed, uneducated and refugees", aiming at fostering the social and labour inclusion of vulnerable groups through a stronger cooperation between Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE) actors and public administrations (Palestine, Jordan, Lebanon, Italy, Greece).

CESIE also presented a paper on the Italian TAIS, titled "All You Can Learn: Increasing Learners' Decision-Making Capacity Through Selective Education Experiences with Highly Vulnerable Groups Among the Forcibly Displaced. Pilot Experience in Palermo, Italy", at ICERI2021 – International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation, celebrated on the 7th-8th November 2021 (<https://library.iated.org/view/ARDIZZONE2021ALL>).

Finland

As has been written in several deliverables from the Finnish perspective, the reception system in Finland is a highly bounded institution with few connections to other societal spheres. Therefore, almost all communication related to TAIS have taken place within this system. The Finnish Red Cross has been a key partner and their reception centres have been informed quite thoroughly throughout the project. The Finnish team has arranged various events with the reception centre professionals and Red Cross experts to share information about the TAIS. Moreover, they have constantly communicated via e-mails, e-meetings and phone calls with reception centres and tried to reach as many asylum seekers as possible through them as well. Professionals, in turn, have informed the asylum-seeking families of their centres. In interview situations and the participatory observation, parents were informed about the project and project activities.

Moreover, the advisory board has been informed and discussed the TAIS activities in annual meetings. The general public has been informed about the problem TAIS is targeting (not the TAIS itself) via an opinion piece in a newspaper article. People responsible for early education and care in the Ministry of education and culture have been informed about the development work via email, and furthermore, officials of some municipalities were informed when carrying out the interviews in the second round.

Hungary

The Hungarian team reached out to most of the refugee-specific organisations who were actively shaping and taking part in the process. ARU members were crucial in this process, but also other invited stakeholders could take part in several activities.

Highlights of the involvement of stakeholders and providing information about the TAIS include the following ARU meetings:

- ARU meeting on 2 April 2020, discussing the interview analysis results, and the outcome of the best practice collection. Introducing the action plan for the following period.
- ARU meeting on 11 September 2020, discussing anonymised case descriptions and exploring the situation and the possibilities of action.
- ARU meeting on 16 March 2021, TAIS Round 2 results - reflections from the participating organisations.

Also, a "Train the trainers" session was held on May 4, 2021, for social workers of other organisations, based on the TAIS, sharing the concept of vulnerability and jointly showcasing training activities that address this topic. This was followed by an enhanced ARU meeting on 26 May 2021 with new members, facilitating a conversation and reflections on the TAIS with intercultural mediators. Yet another enhanced ARU meeting was held on October 11, 2021 with new members, including local level service providers in related fields.

Menedék reached external stakeholders using social media and online platforms: they have an active Facebook account with regular updates about the TAIS, Menedék's website offered up-to-date information and several Newsletters summarised the TAIS results.

Turkey

During the TAIS design process, ARU members were constantly informed and invited to participate. The team designed the trainings for the municipal social workers in collaboration with the ARU members. In this process, each of the ARU members added new members from their own circles to the project. The team used structured communication channels to communicate with both the ARU members and the TAIS participants. They were constantly in touch via the WhatsApp groups set up for the project. The groups AU team reached in collaboration with the ARU members include, among others, the forcibly displaced people themselves, members of NGOs, local government employees, university students, academic staff and members of the Eskişehir artist community. While the project team used these WhatsApp groups to inform about the trainings and meetings, the participants also used them to ask questions and clarify doubts about the project. Also, personnel from Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality,

Tepebaşı Municipality and Odunpazarı Municipality participated in the WhatsApp groups. While the trainings mainly targeted the Metropolitan Municipality employees who provide widespread service to FDP, the team also informed other district municipalities about the project through these groups. In addition, Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality announced the trainings through its internal communication channels.

Within the scope of external communication and dissemination, the Turkish team opened Facebook, Twitter and Instagram accounts specifically for RAISD Anadolu University. They shared the news of the TAIS pilots, and also, the main training sessions were conducted simultaneously using these online channels. They reached social scientists, opinion leaders, industry professionals and students working on immigrants in Turkey, especially in Eskişehir, through their social media accounts. In addition, Anadolu team used social media to introduce the project to two other universities in Eskişehir, Eskişehir Technical University and Osmangazi University.

University staff was updated about TAIS trainings by regularly published bulletins at Anadolu University website and via internal communication email services.

Jordan

ARUs, stakeholders (from education, Law, Health, and economic fields), NGOs and experts interested in providing psychological support in the above mentioned field were informed about the whole TAIS process and services. YU team also conducted a face to face workshop where they presented the TAIS process. Also, publicising the TAIS process and services was done through national media channels and social media pages.

Lebanon

The design of the TAIS program and implementation of the evaluation process relied on LIU's health committee which focused on direct engagements amongst each other and the beneficiaries.

In the initial phase of the ARU design, LIU staff members, IT personnel, Physicians who work with vulnerable maternity cases, UNRWA, and NGOS Tatwer Baldna and SPARK, researchers and even the Ex Minister of Foreign and Trade Affairs were reached and set as a work team (ARU), and then communicated with and invited to partake in both the ARU meetings and workshops. It should be noted that all LIU team members can attest to having previous work experiences in projects related to displaced people, therefore their personal networks were useful for the initial communication with potential stakeholders, e.g UNRWA.

These ARU members participated during the whole course of the process, especially during the peak of pandemic and during the Beirut blast.

The communication was primarily conducted through email and phone calls. As for the Health committee, there was a log of meetings with all members attending. Minutes were taken to keep track of all the measures taken in terms of improving the TAIS.

The external communication posted news about the TAIS via social media and online channels such as the Lets E talk newsletter, Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn accounts. The team also distributed the RAISD newsletter about the TAIS among their stakeholders.

5 TAIS impacts and challenges

5.1 *Impacts of the TAIS in the lives of the beneficiaries*

The principal aim of the TAIS in the 7 participating countries was twofold: on the one hand, direct support to FDP in Finland, Italy, Jordan and Spain and on the other, capacity building and professional improvement for persons who work with FDP in Hungary, Turkey and Lebanon. It is within the reach of the TAIS research to resume the partner countries stakeholder's expectation on the potential impacts and to gather their impressions about how well the TAIS succeeded in reaching those goals. Confirming the actual impacts on the beneficiaries' inclusion and integration process are more difficult to assess, especially if we consider that most of the TAIS might affect FDP integration in the medium or long term. As stated by HU team, the impacts are probably quite modest and not necessarily seen in the outcome measures, as with almost all interventions in the social spheres of human action. For the above mentioned reasons, the current subchapter is centred on the principal short term impacts in the lives of the TAIS beneficiaries, FDPs and people who assist them. The data provided by partners comes mainly from interviews, ARU meetings and focus groups, as well as direct observation of the core TAIS implementation teams.

In many cases, the expectation about the desirable outcomes changed along the TAIS process, when the personal situation of the beneficiaries changed or conditions turned different in the local context, but in general terms, the impressions collected from the diverse stakeholders seem to confirm that the TAIS had positive impacts on the lives of the beneficiaries, at least on short term. For both types of beneficiaries, FDP and people who work with them, the TAIS generally contributed to enhanced capacities and professional skills, and in the case of the FDP, also to improved autonomy, fostering traits related to interpersonal relationships, self-confidence and gender awareness. These improved capacities, skills and personal traits are expected to have a progressive impact on the social and professional inclusion and integration of the migrants that participated in the programs and to improve the motivational and work related aspects of the persons who work in forced migration.

The current report reproduces stakeholder impressions and insights on the most relevant TAIS impacts, it does not delve into details related with the TAIS systematic evaluation methods and outcomes, as these are explained in other three publicly available reports. A detailed explanation of the TAIS evaluation measures is included in D7.4 Evaluation criteria: actor-oriented and integrated evaluation criteria, whereas the global evaluation outcomes and process are described in D7.2 Cross-analysis workshop results. The success elements of the TAIS are analysed in D5.3 TAIS definition and guidelines (all the mentioned reports are available at the RAISD website <https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>).

In Spain, the impacts expected when the TAIS was being designed slightly changed after the team gained a deeper knowledge on the specific needs, knowledge gaps and professional aspirations of the beneficiaries. Initially, both self-employment (founding a cooperative) and improving employability were contemplated, but later on, the idea of

a cooperative was dropped as participants emphasised their preference for improved employment opportunities and training contents on IT, job seeking and specific professional skills. In Italy, the strength of the ALL you can LEARN program was delivering the courses in the field, in the CAS centres. The beneficiaries improved not only their professional skills, but also their decision making skills and felt involved in the process, and the hands-on part of the training served to match wishes and expectations with actual possibilities and competences. The initiative jointly delivered by CESIE and the Freedom centre was considered a success for the inclusion and integration of the women beneficiaries of the TAIS. In Finland, TAIS I program consisting of a multilingual online forum had a positive impact on the inclusion and integration of the beneficiaries, in terms of an increased trust between asylum-seeking and Finnish-speaking men and improved language and cultural knowledge of the host country. The TAIS II, the childcare service in reception centres, contributed to decreased levels of stress and anxiety and increased subjective well-being of the migrant families that benefited from the program. In Hungary, the aim of the TAIS was to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures by providing tools for social workers, so they could easily analyse individual cases and find helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. It eases the burden of social workers in the short term and will have indirect effects on FDP inclusion and integration processes. In Turkey, Anadolu University TAIS focused on developing the capacity of municipal social workers to address the vulnerabilities of forcibly displaced persons in the context of rights-based and needs-based problems. The facilitators noticed the impacts of the training in terms of changing attitudes of the social workers because they had gained a better understanding of the vulnerabilities of the FDP. In Jordan, the TAIS aimed at enabling FDPs to become agents of transformative change in their own lives, households, and in the life of their communities. The implementation team noticed an unexpected positive impact of the training as the participating FDPs became more aware of their own legal rights. In Lebanon, the self-directed learning and capacity building of the training sessions are expected to have an impact in the camps, where those Syrian refugees that participated in the TAIS training can transfer their learning outcomes and become trainers themselves.

Spain

Regarding their expectations, all the beneficiaries affirm that they want to get a stable job so that they can buy a home in Madrid and be able to live without sharing a flat, without having to pay rent or without depending on an NGO. Two of them say that they would like to be able to save money to start an association and return to their country, buy a house there and give work to young people from their place of origin.

Improving their social support network has been also considered by means of the TAIS, generating a support network among women from different places of origin and with different mother tongues. Finally, some of them have developed some kind of friendship ties with each other. Something relevant, since their spirits are low because they affirm that they are alone and feel lonely and that this affects them a lot when looking for a job or doing any other task. Moreover, it is very difficult for them to develop deeper levels of friendship in Spain so they cannot tell their problems as they would with friends, which makes them very sad.

Throughout the training and the mentoring program, an attempt has been made to improve their autonomy and responsibility for their self-learning, avoiding behaviours of dependence on the workers of the entities or third parties. Its use in new technologies has improved, which also improves their communication and relationship with

different entities and with the administration, increasing their social and personal autonomy. The improvement in their knowledge of bureaucratic aspects also allows them to interact with different organisations in a more proactive way.

The initial goal established in the ARU workshops was providing the participants with tools and skills for entrepreneurship, providing them a starting point for founding a cooperative, to directly improve their employment situation. Some of the participants had initially thought that the program would set up the cooperative for them and in this sense, they experienced some deception when they found out that the aim was rather providing the tools and training them for entrepreneurship. Anyway, this initial idea was soon found to be a bit too ambitious as the beneficiaries did not find it feasible and within the reach of their possibilities, especially in terms of their economic capacity and confidence to start this kind of large initiative in a foreign country.

Another important goal was to improve the beneficiaries' employability with capacity building in terms of linguistic, professional, job-seeking, IT, administrative, business skills, etc., as well as fostering traits related to interpersonal relationships, self-confidence and gender awareness. The second goal was reached as all the participants improved their performance in most of the above-mentioned fields. Linguistic and communicative improvements are of great importance for these women, since one of the hardest situations that they remember from their stay in Spain is arriving in a country alone with a language that is totally unknown.

We can conclude that the program had a positive impact on the capacities building, self-knowledge and confidence of the participants, as well as on their awareness of tools and techniques for setting up a business and job seeking. In most cases, the training and the mentoring improved the beneficiaries' motivation for employment. In half of the cases, the participants found a new job or set up a small online business during the training period, so these can be considered fulfilled expectations. As an unexpected positive impact, we could consider the fact that three of the participants launched themselves to found small online businesses. This has an important impact on their lives, since the expectations these women had about the TAIS were related to their work market possibilities. In terms of self-confidence, the empowerment test carried out in March 2021 showed that the participants felt they had experienced improvements and also, they felt they received more support from the group.

Nevertheless, the expectations to highly improve the beneficiaries' social engagement via personal contacts between them and with the persons providing training, entities they would have visited if it had not been for the Covid 19 restrictions etc., could not be fully met. In terms of unexpected negative impacts, there were none of consideration. Still, the lack of personal contact with the beneficiaries might have caused some frustration both in the trainers and trainees.

All the women thought that the professionals who worked with them in RAISD and in the workshops, even by telematic means, behaved very well with them and that they were happy with the project, because it gave them an opportunity to interact with other women in the same kind of situation and to learn from the participating professionals who also gave them emotional support. Some participants stated that this project gave them hope to get a good future job, some even succeeded to improve their professional situation during the training.

The African ladies that participated in the learning session had diverse views about the ideas that the trainers might have about their performance. Half of them expressed that the trainers must have been happy with them as they made great efforts, were punctual and accomplished the tasks they were asked to do. Having the recognition of the trainers was indeed comforting and important for the participants. The other half thought that the lecturers would have wanted to see more participation. Due to the lack of time or scarce computer knowledge, some of the beneficiaries missed a considerable number of sessions, ignoring their homework and being non-participative during the sessions.

Italy

The opportunity to work inside the CAS centre and to cooperate with the managers of the facility made a highly positive and performing impact possible. All women improved their decision-making skills and felt involved. Participants underlined how this cooperation mode made them feel like the authors of their own personal and professional growth project, learning new transversal skills but also growing in terms of language and knowledge of the territory in which they live. It was unanimously stated by the participants that the activities carried out in a moment of isolation (due to covid-19 and its general restrictions) gave them hope for the future.

In addition, all activities were supported by technological equipment brought into the centre by CESIE, such as laptops and tablets. This made the participants' technological skills grow vertically and progressively and increased their curiosity and active participation during all the sessions.

As stated by the first testimony of the Italian ARU Stories (<https://cesie.org/en/higher-education-and-research/raisd-research-testimonials/>) comes from Mr Giuseppe Spinelli, an educator of the Freedom centre, a centre working with trafficked women. CESIE partnered with "Cooperativa Nuova Generazione, Freedom centre" in the nearby town of Trabia (20 km distance from Palermo) to implement the TAIS, contributing to the integration and inclusion of the vulnerable women arriving to the centre by arranging training sessions with and for them. Point of strength of the Italian ARU has been working on the territory and collaborating with different stakeholders, putting in place a network of operators from different fields to achieve the highest impact on the beneficiaries. Giuseppe highlights in his testimony the great enthusiasm and satisfaction of the young women for the opportunity offered by CESIE, and the participation in the training session was indeed massive. Among the main strengths of the TAIS and the work of the ARU, he noticed the capacity to break down the cultural and language barriers, and the ability of making the training highly interactive, engaging the participating women not only in the learning as such but also involving them emotionally, paying attention to their feelings during the process. The testimony is available here: <https://youtu.be/D-ALH805j7I>.

The second testimonial of the Italian ARU Stories is Ms Luigia Sunseri, one of the educators of the Freedom centre. During her interview, she immediately highlighted the importance of having the training delivered directly by CESIE at the centre. That was a key element for the girls hosted in the centre, increasing their feelings of confidence, security, protection and wellbeing. Noteworthy was the great capacity on behalf of CESIE to involve the young women in the training, raising their curiosity and providing them with support in their path to the future. The hands-on part of the training was essential to match wishes and expectations with actual possibilities and competences. The initiative jointly delivered by CESIE and the Freedom centre was indeed a success for the inclusion and integration

of the women, also looking at the long-term perspective it may open for them, towards a new independent space for their own lives. At the very end of her intervention, Luigia stressed the constructive and fruitful collaboration put in place with CESIE, that the centre welcomed very positively, and will be ready to welcome in the future as well. The testimony is available here: <https://raisd-h2020.eu/research/aru/italy/>.

Finland

The aim was to promote the inclusion and capacities of asylum-seeking men. In this case, inclusion refers to increased trust between asylum-seeking and Finnish-speaking men and lowered threshold in approaching each other. As for the capacities, the aim was to improve asylum seekers' skills in everyday written language and lower the threshold in using it. Moreover, capacities refer to increased knowledge of Finnish culture and institutions. Further, for Finnish-speaking men improved capacities refer to increased knowledge and understanding of the rights and living conditions of asylum seekers in Finland.

The aim was to promote the well-being of asylum-seeking families. For parents, access to child-care services enables them to invest time in various activities, use of services, studying and rest. Consequently, the potential outcome of the pilot would be decreased levels of stress and anxiety and increased subjective wellbeing. Moreover, the TAIS would possibly increase parents' autonomy while they have free time they can use how they wish. Also, inclusion and capacities may increase while parents can invest their time in studying. Obviously, participating in good-quality childcare activities has the potential to foster the wellbeing and learning of children, and alleviate the possible anxieties of children stemming from forced displacement.

A positive impact related to service providers is their enthusiasm towards the development work, as they are trying to keep the more intensive structure of the child-care services after the trial period via other funding sources. A negative impact may be service providers' tendency to bind child-care activities to parents' activities happening in the meantime, while the parents wish to get more free time in addition to the chance to take part in the study and other activities.

The outcome evaluations of the two Finnish TAIS is still in the making so it is too early to say much about the results. However, one can assume that not all the goals will be met. In terms of the online forum, one of the setbacks was the limited number of participants – the potential impact could have been wider. When it comes to the childcare service, the trial will probably have a positive impact on the parent while it is going on, but it is harder to evaluate long-term impacts. Moreover, as with almost all interventions in the social spheres of human action, the impacts (if there are any) are probably quite modest and not necessarily seen in the outcome measures.

No unexpected negative or positive impacts have been observed.

Hungary

In Hungary, the objective of the TAIS is to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures. Social workers analyse individual cases in order to build a "Trajectory monitoring toolbox" of helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. It contains evidence-based "vulnerability profiles" and the description of the trajectories that

these typical cases should follow in the institutional field to prevent the accumulation of vulnerabilities and reduce the isolation of vulnerable individuals. Social workers and service providers in Budapest should be informed about who, where, and how to apply helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees.

To achieve the main objective the TAIS, by the end of the last phase two main products was created:

1. Handbook. We transferred the research results of vulnerability contexts into training exercises, offering a practical task collection that processes the vulnerability of refugees living in Hungary along with current, real-life situations. In this handbook, vulnerability is described as a situation in which there is an increased risk that an individual will be harmed in some way or suffer a social or legal disadvantage that seriously affects their living conditions. It is a long-standing circumstance that limits the satisfaction of basic needs, threatens access to human rights, or even threatens identity. Another indicator of vulnerability is that the individual needs special care, support or protection in this situation.

2. Self-reflection tool. Based on the results of mapping the vulnerability contexts, we concluded that service providers are playing a pivotal role in vulnerability reduction. We have noticed that there is no framework for self-reflection neither in forms of reporting, nor in working relationships, furthermore its importance is not emphasised in the institutional level. To address the lack of self-reflection in the daily practices of service providers, we built a new pilot program involving the social workers, and ARUs to develop a methodological system.

Turkey

In particular, during the ARU meetings, forcibly displaced people very clearly voiced their problems in accessing health, education, sheltering, employment, decision-making processes, inclusion to the host community and other rights-based and need-based variables in everyday life.

In particular, the RAISD project developed a capacity for assistance that the municipality can offer indirectly, through the social services department, to the forcibly displaced people. RAISD project built a bridge between forcibly displaced people and municipalities in Eskişehir.

Furthermore, it was an unexpected positive outcome of the RAISD project that Eskişehir Bar Association took action on vulnerability and discrimination. Eskişehir Bar Association took initiatives to establish new projects with local government stakeholders on these issues.

The goal of Anadolu University RAISD TAIS was to develop the capacity of municipal social workers to address the vulnerabilities of forcibly displaced persons in the context of rights-based and needs-based problems. In this context, trainings were given to social workers under the headings of diversity, inclusion and monitoring. During the training, the most important finding was that social workers did not refer to forcibly displaced people as vulnerable persons. They did not even think of them being forcibly displaced. After the trainings and the discussions social workers become aware of this and could acknowledge what these concepts mean and tell who can be considered vulnerable and forcibly displaced. As a result of the trainings, all the municipal personnel that participated in the courses

embrace this idea and are willing to continue the trainings. Along the sessions, the participants realised their knowledge shortcomings on vulnerable groups and demanded the continuation of the training activity.

Jordan

Through the evaluation of the TAIS, the Jordanian team expects that the TAIS will have a positive impact on the lives of the beneficiaries, FDPs and ARUs. For FDPs, the TAIS addresses psychological support in five main fields. One of its main objectives is to enable FDPs to become instruments / agents of transformative change in their own lives, households, and in the life of their communities. One of the unexpected positive impacts was within the legal empowerment field as many FDPs were not aware of their legal rights in the host community. The team also realised that there is a huge change within the mind-set of FDPs after spending almost 10 years in Jordan. At the beginning, refugees were focussing on survival and attaining their basic needs. What the team noticed during the implementation process, through the question-answer responses, was that refugees are willing to improve their conditions via education, entrepreneurship, and self-psychological treatment. They utilise what they learn from training programs to improve their livelihoods.

As for ARUs, the TAIS methodology was an effective methodology that infused the ARUs to follow in order to develop their own training designs.

Lebanon

It should be noted that the HE students have formed good relationships with their instructors and developed rapport.

During the training program self-directed learning was established. The advancement of their knowledge of inter and intra personal competences means that they will be able to better adapt to new situations.

It can be concluded that the program undoubtedly had a positive influence on elements such as capacity building, self-directed and digital learning and on developing leadership attitudes among the Syrian students, so they could become support member of the communities and coaches in their camps.

The lack of personal, face to face contact with the beneficiaries may have potentially generated some level of anxiety and frustration amongst both the trainers and trainees. Human and face to face contact produces more effective outcomes with stronger impact.

5.2 Eventual ethical issues in the application of the TAIS

Ethics is an aspect that is often taken for granted in R&I projects, as it is closely related to accomplishing with legal principles and the most relevant codes of conduct in the field of the study in question, which seem easy to meet with. Nevertheless, these are only the starting point for constructing a solid ethical framework for a new research initiative as each project needs to reflect about the ethical boundaries and offer guidelines for its daily research and innovation practice.

To start with, RAISD project research and innovation activities respond to the requirements of The European Commission's guidance note about Research on refugees, asylum seekers and migrants: "Research on refugees, asylum seekers and migrants concerns a particularly vulnerable group which needs particular safeguards in terms of research ethics" (2020, p.1). In practice, this transferred to RAISD research and innovation meant making field research (interviews, surveys, etc.) comprehensive for all the participants, informing in a clear way about their rights and what the information is used for, about what they agree to when giving their informed permission, about their right to withdraw from the project at any moment, making participants feel at ease and experience privacy, being sensitive to religious, gender and cultural diversities, and especially to vulnerabilities (briefing researchers and trainers about the vulnerability contexts of the participants). Ethical dumping (e.g. accepting laxer rules that might apply in non-European countries) was totally unacceptable and the strictest norms prevailed, especially in terms of privacy and data transfer.

Aspects related to the personal data protection and privacy, anonymisation of research data and acquiring informed consent are at the core of RAISD research, with a special focus on guaranteeing that the forcibly displaced migrants needing protection and that participate in the project cannot be identified, traced back, localised or exposed to situation that can elsewhere jeopardise their safety and integrity. RAISD complies with the European data protection and data movement regulations, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679 as well as the national regulations in the participating countries. RAISD has published two deliverables related to privacy and data protection. On the one hand, D9.1 Data management plan (DMP) describes the data management life cycle for all data sets that are collected, processed or generated by the research project (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/process-oriented-results/>). It also specifies the methodology and standards for the data management and whether these data are to be shared and/or made open and how data are curated and preserved. This plan complies with the template provided by the European Commission in Annex 1: Horizon 2020 FAIR data management plan template (EC, 2016). On the other hand, D9.2 Privacy plan focuses on the security and confidentiality of data in the software of the project. It includes the measures to avoid any undesired disclosure of information (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/process-oriented-results/>).

To ensure a fair and ethical research and innovation process, RAISD follows the guidelines of European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2017) in compliance with the principles of:

- Reliability in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources.
- Honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent and fair way.
- Respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and environment.
- Accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts.

In general, most of the challenges related to ethics took place during the project research phase, but the same rules apply to the innovation phase: the design, practice and evaluation of the TAIS. Privacy rules were applied to each context to guarantee that all TAIS activities address security, ethics and individual freedom as well as privacy of the

participants. Probably the biggest ethical challenge in all the participating countries was the actual engagement of the FDP in the whole TAIS process, achieved after some initial difficulties. The focus of the TAIS was on the empowerment of FDP and persons who work with them, avoiding patronising approaches, fostering practices and language that fight stigmatisation of FDP. In terms of incidental findings, none were reported by the partners, though the project had a committee for such occasions. Maximum care was given to a fair recruiting process of the TAIS beneficiaries, based on equal opportunities for all eligible participants.

In Spain, the main issue was the slightly patronising nature of the TAIS coordination team, an error which was remedied soon after the reporting. Italy reported no ethics related difficulties, and one of the most interesting points of engagement was the signing of a Letter of Commitment of the participants (a practice that permitted to reduce course dropout) and the Release of use of Likeness document (where CESIE commits to not to use such images and likenesses in manners that might be offensive to the dignity and reputation of the undersigned). In Finland, the team faced difficulties in explaining the reach of the online forum as well as with minor privacy issues related to it as some participants shared private data (in search of work opportunities). Also, as happened in other countries, explaining and getting informed consent (verbal or written) to research and innovation settings that involve participatory observation was tricky. In Hungary, the privacy of primary documents was well guarded and no ethical issues raised in their TAIS focused on providing tools for social workers. At all times, the team followed both Menedék code of ethics and RAISD ethics guide recommendation. In Turkey, the team took additional measures to protect the privacy and confidentiality of the participating municipal workers, whereas Jordan and Lebanon reported no significant ethical issues.

RAISD ethics regulations are explained in D3.1 Ethics Plan, and in two publicly available additional manuals for researchers: D3.2.1 Interview guidelines, D3.2.2 Information related to Ethics and Gender Issues (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>). They provide guidelines to data collection and interviews, informed consent, anonymity of interviewed people, compensation to participants, gender perspective, multi-perspective analysis, participatory assessment and instructions for the Covid-19 context. To ensure ethics principles were widely applied in the project, ethical reminders were included in several Consortium meeting discussions, and simplified internal guides (on interviews, gender, informed consent) and advice was provided whenever necessary.

In the following, partner countries provide more detailed information on their main ethical challenges and how they dealt with them.

Spain

In the second TAIS evaluation round, some participants mentioned that the focus of the Spanish TAIS was occasionally a bit too patronising as the beneficiaries received a very close follow-up, something that from the organising team was considered necessary (e.g. sending reminders to connect to lessons). After that notice, the team tried to avoid this kind of small paternalistic expressions, sometimes at the risk of losing participation level. Still, this can be considered a minor issue and requires no changes for the Ethics plan.

Another idea for improvement was expressed by some of the service providers and beneficiaries, referring to the inclusion of all the beneficiaries in the initial design of the training program. This was difficult to put into practice, as

for the recruitment of participants, the team needed to have an initial program. At the design phase, these future participants were obviously not present, though the team had other representatives from FDP groups in the first ARU meetings. A meeting was held in June 2020 with 12 possible beneficiaries of the TAIS in order to validate the design of the TAIS to better understand their profiles and gather new needs and expectations (3 simultaneous meetings via WhatsApp videoconference, as it was the only tool they knew). The contents proposed by the ARU members for the training were mentioned to them and validated. Clearly, that was insufficient as the beneficiaries should have participated more actively from the very beginning in the design of the TAIS. Once the team realised the TAIS design did not fully match the beneficiaries' expectations, new ideas were collected and changes were included in the design. This aspect is already included in the RAISD Ethics Plan, in terms of fostering FDP participation in all the phases of the project.

UCM team debated whether, if necessary, to include the name and image of those forcibly displaced people who, being aware of their situation and possible risks, wanted to appear in the communication of the TAIS activities, for example, in the case of activist refugees. Finally, no beneficiary of the TAIS expressed that wish (there were no activists among TAIS beneficiaries), so it was not necessary to continue with the debate.

Italy

Ethics and privacy issues at Italian ARU during [Vulnerability Profiling and FDP Fieldwork](#):

CESIE's research team paid particular attention to sensitive and ethical issues since the recruitment phase of potential research fieldwork participants, during the actual interview recording (mainly within welcome shelters, community centres, women shelters and at our Competence Cell facilities at CESIE office), through the audio's anonymised transcription and translation process (no external service provision needed) and the privacy management of the gathered information (stored on secured CESIE's servers). All interview transcriptions are recorded and stored with an assigned anonymisation code.

The official "Consent Form" template was developed by UCM, D3.2 Work Methodology, and has been translated into Italian, thus researchers were provided with both printouts and each interviewee could sign the Italian or English version consent form.

Researchers (1 female English-speaking/Swahili/Kimeru/Kikuiu and 1 male French-speaking/Wolof) were asked to be prepared to go through the consent form with the 25 interviewed FDP, in detail, in the national/regional language/dialect they would adopt to conduct the full interview, to ensure all points are well understood.

Moreover, founding elements of the Transparent Research approach have been taken into consideration particularly during fieldwork activities, the findings of which (data collection, analysis, and report writing) have led to the identification of TAIS main target beneficiaries and to highlight peculiar needs to be addressed by a novelty strategy to implement.

Due to ethical issues the openness of data has been partially restricted to not compromise anonymity of research participants, producing only qualitative analyses and making aggregate level data available to the ARU members and

the wider working groups through the dedicated website section. Open access will further be improved so that data can potentially be reanalysed and synthesised by academics in future studies and by practitioners and managers for interventions planning.

Ethics and privacy issues at Italian ARU during TAIS implementation rounds:

All AULC participants from both piloting groups, were introduced and invited to sign:

- Learners' contract (Declaration of commitment to participate in the full learning programme).
- Ethics & Privacy consent form.
- Release of use of Likeness: document - to obtain and use as the Released Party sees fit the voice, image, photograph, likeness, video, and/or any other form of media as it develops (henceforth collectively referred to as Likeness). CESIE meanwhile undertakes not to use such images and likenesses in manners that might be offensive to the dignity and reputation of the undersigned.
- (GROUP1) Covid-19 Substitute Declaration/Affidavit.

All Mentors of GROUP1 signed a Confidentiality/Non-disclosure Agreement: to clarify that sensitive and personal information of participants, as well as development strategies discussed in monitoring meetings – remain strictly confidential.

Both TAIS co-implementers signed the 'Release of use of Likeness' document when recording their video testimonies for the D7.1 ARU Research Stories.

The AUCL Privacy Policy statement is included in the footer of the <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/privacy> portal.

No major ethical issues surged along the TAIS piloting process. There are no further suggestions to the current ethical plan.

Finland

There have been at least two types of ethical issues related to the online forum. First, there was the issue of language and informed consent. In some cases, it seemed as if asylum seekers had had some difficulties in understanding what the forum is about despite information letters in different languages. Therefore, there has been a need to stress the aim and nature of the forum on several occasions to avoid too high expectations or plain misunderstandings. Second, there have been some problems with data protection and revealing identities and quite private issues in the online platform. Some asylum seekers have needed help in, for instance, finding work or coping with various administrative processes. Obviously, providing them enough help through an online site is a very challenging job. Moreover, to clarify some issues or to help in writing job applications, some discussants have posted their private documents including sensitive personal information to the platform. These documents have obviously been helpful but at the same time there was a risk of them being leaked to people who might exploit them.

Ethical reflections were central throughout the whole TAIS process starting from interviews to ending the trial. The main ethical principle of the research and developmental work is to go beyond the principle of 'do no harm'. This means respecting participants' (and stakeholders') autonomy and their status as unique individuals while simultaneously recognising asylum seekers' subordinate status in the Finnish society. To do more than just avoid harming people means to come up with real-life solutions to their problems in the form of co-production of TAIS. Obviously, for most asylum seekers, the problems are immediate, and the slowness of research probably feels frustrating. These types of limitations have been explained to participants in their own languages in the best possible manner.

One ethical issue when researching already existing services is the question of consent. In participatory observation in on-going services the negotiation of the consent is not simple: it is not to ensure that participants have rightly understood the purpose of the presence of the researcher. However, parents were informed about the research in their own languages. Another ethical issue raised when developing an already existing service required balancing and considering both parents and services providers perspectives. Close co-operation with service providers was essential while they were the actual providers of the services and improvements needed to be accepted, agreed and finally implemented by them. At the same time, the perspective of the main beneficiaries, the FDP, should be at the core of the developing activities and their needs are important to be communicated to service providers, even though the perspectives of these two groups may be somewhat contradictory.

Hungary

The team has followed Menedek's Code of Ethics and the RAISD Ethics Plan during the TAIS process.

Ethical concerns have been observed regarding the participants and the primary materials as well. Therefore, as the texts are internal, working materials were read only by RAISD core staff (not even the ARU will have access to the original texts). Moreover, published materials will be anonymised, and it will not be possible to trace who were the interviewees, authors, and clients.

Turkey

ARU members, forcibly displaced people involved in our project and Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality social workers who participated in the training did not want their identities to be revealed. We, as the RAISD Anadolu University team, complied with this within the scope of the RAISD ethics plan.

Jordan

The Jordan team reported that no ethical issues surged along the TAIS process.

Lebanon

There was no problem in this area. Yet in Lebanon, the team considered that due to the local context and difficulties faced, they would have needed more time to (1) analyse the consequences; (2) analyse the actions; (3) study the

decisions. The project coordination team alleviated the time concern, giving considerable extra time for delivering reports to those partners who had difficulties (UCM observation).

5.3 Challenges related to the methodological approach

RAISD methodology can sometimes be very challenging due to the novelty of the combination of RRI, AR and Socio-ecological models. RRI is still an emerging discipline in European research and its epistemological principles are under constant reflection. The collaborative and inclusive approach to research that means engaging all the relevant stakeholders is time consuming and makes decision making slower. The concepts of research democracy, deep ethics, sustainability and responsibility are broad and demanding when applied to research and innovation activities in real life settings. The quest for a crosswise application of a gender in R & I is inherent in the RRI philosophy, and moving from gender-aware approaches to gender-sensitive approaches was at the same time a must and a challenge to the consortium, a requirement that was well met at the end. AR is in itself a demanding research method as it requires great flexibility and capacity to adapt to the changes and constant revisions. AR often demands a participatory research and innovation approach, meaning that researchers and strategy implementers need to become sensitive to diversity and vulnerability related aspects of the research context. Socio-ecological levels make research data and results clustering easier, but analysing the interrelations between micro, meso and macro level is complex and demands both methodological and conceptual preparation of the research teams. The TAIS took place in demanding real life settings, with important changes in local context and with the socio sanitary emergency of the Covid-19 outbreak, which put to prove the RRI dimensions of anticipation, reflexion, capacity of response and adaptive change (Owen et al., 2013). SMART criteria was used for the implementation of the innovative TAIS with the aim of strategy being specific, measurable, attainable, relevant and time-based. In SMART, the M of measurable marked a difficulty for the partners, as the TAIS outcomes and impacts are mostly qualitative.

In Spain, the main challenge was related to explaining and providing methodological advice to the partners and in terms of the TAIS, fostering all stakeholder groups' participation. In Italy, the trace of migrants' complex trajectories, their trauma, stress symptoms and health conditions sometimes often made it difficult to engage FDP in the TAIS. Developing a training course for and with FDP that are in constant motion, and motivating them was quite a challenge. In Finland, the team emphasises the challenge of combining a highly micro-level orientation of action research methodology and socio-ecological thinking. The Hungarian team reported some difficulties in engaging FDP in the design of the TAIS as it was aimed at social workers. Also, when it comes to SMART criteria, the aspect of 'measurable' was not within the reach of the project, though other criteria could be met. In Turkey, the team focused on Socio-ecological modelling and interpretation of interactions between levels of activity, and in this sense, the team shared a methodology learning experience with the TAIS beneficiaries. The Jordan team expressed some difficulties in putting into practice the theory and shared with the Lebanese team a concern about the time pressure; both would have needed more time for Covid-19 adaptations. The Lebanese team also recognizes that a thorough FDP needs analysis would have made the TAIS process easier.

Spain

UCM as a coordinating partner and responsible for WP3 (Methodological coordination) had good knowledge of the methodology, but still, it was challenging to share the methodology guidelines so that all the R&I team participants would have a clear picture of what was required from them. Also, the collaborative work systems (as part of the RRI philosophy) sometimes made decision making slower.

Part of the partners, as they made clear in the bilateral meetings with UCM, would have needed some additional training on the methodological aspects at the very beginning of the project, though these were later on dealt with in the consortium meetings and also, several guides on methodological issues were distributed among partners. Also, partners received on-demand individual advice and support for methodological issues such as the initial research, TAIS design or deliverables. Truth to be told, the pandemics hindered organising face-to-face meetings and workshops among partners, which would have provided a better floor for sharing knowledge on the methodology and for collective learning. Still, as a conclusion and self-critic, UCM could have been more proactive in this sense.

As other partners, UCM had some challenges and practical difficulties when applying the methodology to the TAIS design, implementation and evaluation. In the specific case of TAIS beneficiaries, they have not participated in ARU meetings except on rare occasions, such as TAIS evaluations, due to their Spanish level and the difficulty of participating on equal terms with social services providers. Nevertheless, other forced migrants have actively participated in ARU meetings. The team considers that they should have insisted more on the incorporation of TAIS beneficiaries in the ARU. For this purpose, more training and more personalised attention would have been required, the pandemic has made it even more difficult because of lockdowns and online meetings; however, more effort from the UCM team could have been expended on it.

When it comes to the multistakeholder approach, UCM team had difficulties finding representatives of the business helix. It is something that must be improved for future projects, also with more dedication to find and strengthen business contacts, insisting on the benefits for these organisations. All this would also have an impact on a greater transference and communication of the results, in addition to providing a vision for the project that, from the point of view of RRI and action research, is not fully present. The team believes that it is a difficulty that other ARUs have found, so it would be a common challenge for different countries regardless of the cultural, political, and legal context.

Also, with regard to ARU members and service providers of the TAIS, sometimes it was difficult to count on them at times when more participation was required. TAIS coordinators needed to measure the efforts that were demanded from the ARU members, since some of them, especially those who were directly involved in the TAIS, showed certain fatigue due to all the information and efforts required. To avoid these peaks of increased effort in collaboration, it became necessary to better coordinate and organise information requests from the ARU members. Clearly, this was a challenge to take into account in the application of RRI and action-research, since decision-making cannot be unilateral by the coordinating team, so it depended on the availability of different stakeholders. This is not the case for the Spanish ARU, but if the ARU membership is not numerous enough, the development of the TAIS may be compromised if a stakeholder abandons the initiative.

UCM has developed a valuable and quite numerous ARU, but it is true that RRI and action research also hinder/slow down decision-making in the ARU, as mentioned by different partners. Much transparency and communication efforts are required, so that ARU members do not feel disappointed when their option is not chosen. The key issue to avoid the problem is the anticipation before misunderstandings may arise.

Another challenge has been not losing the participation of ARU members that were not directly involved in the TAIS. UCM pretends to tackle this difficulty by means of the future RAISD Observatory of FD, the online platform where ARU members will be invited to share information and good practices related to their expertise and to develop policy recommendations so their necessities can be heard. The Observatory will especially foster the participation of forced migrants.

Italy

Difficulties and challenges are interlinked with several risk factors that materialised particularly at the participants' socio-ecological micro-level, as the amount of stress, disorientation, psychological and physical discomfort were considerable and influenced the strategies' flow of activities. All participating women come from violent experiences, whose fundamental rights have been violated several times. The stay in these centres is not long, sometimes a woman is transferred to another centre in another region. In addition, women may escape from the centre for desire of independence and autonomy or because they return to mechanisms of violence and coercion from which they could not free themselves. The reason for this is immediate economic gain from prostitution or illegal work.

During the pilot implementation, there have been actual cases where women have left and never returned to the centre, and although all women are supported by an experienced team of psychologists and doctors, many of them have manifested considerable psychic distress and a TSO Compulsory health treatments (Trattamento Sanitario Obbligatorio) occurred on one of the participants. This information is of fundamental importance to understand the intrinsic difficulties within the sector in which the project was implemented, deciding to support one of the most fragile categories of our society.

As highlighted in the RAISD Italian Vulnerability Reports (D4.1, D4.2):

“Access to local health services still operates on an emergency basis, which explains the growing number of emergency admittances and hospitalisations for acute psychiatric disorders among migrants. This figure is also due to a different mode of accessing care for migrants, in which the SPCD (Psychiatric Service of Diagnosis and Treatment) becomes the shorter and easier route of entry, but only when the pathology explodes and is no longer controllable. There is an abuse of compulsory health treatments (Trattamento Sanitario Obbligatorio, TSO in Italian) prescribed on the criterion of the dangerousness. The use of the emergency services remains the most common practice for a quick but unstructured ‘solution’ to the problems”.

In terms of social and health services, there is still a lack of planning, tools and working practices adapted to individuals coming from very different areas and cultures. This is most evident in the Sicilian context according to MSF report Neglected Trauma (2017).

At meso-level, challenges were caused by several reasons:

- Creating a 90 hours training course for women who live in conditions of continuous mobility is not easy; many times they escape from their hosting centres or they move to other places.
- Meeting their motivation to participate to a course that doesn't provide participants an economical income has been proving quite challenging.
- Finding the collaboration of the working staff in the Centres to motivate the women proved also to be a consistent challenge.

Finland

The RAISD methodological framework is highly ambitious and requires deep engagement in the field of study. This engagement has been a challenging thing to do during these exceptional times. Moreover, and probably more fundamentally, it is a great challenge to combine a highly micro-level orientation of action research methodology and socio-ecological thinking. I am not sure if we have been able to seize all these quite different dimensions.

Moreover, there might be some (mostly quite technical) challenges with the RRI perspective. As far as the team knows, it is designed for quite different purposes (technology and industry) than projects such as RAISD mainly drawing from social sciences. For social sciences, there might be more relevant methodological guidelines to secure the inclusion of key stakeholders and perspectives.

Hungary

Menédek did the implementation of TAIS based on the following ethical and methodological foundations: Socio-ecological models, RRI, AR Strategy and SMART Criteria.

Concerning the Socio-ecological models, the TAIS was conceptualised having in mind the social and political "ecosystem" in which it took place. Three levels of intervention were distinguished:

1. Micro level: individual / interpersonal. Family and affective-emotional context. Very relevant in the Hungarian case.
2. Meso level: institutional. Interactions with communities of origin, receiving communities during transit and at destination, contexts of groups and associations, etc. Also relevant in the Hungarian context, yet, it is rather fragmented (and has to operate in a hostile political climate).
3. Macro level: policy / law. It was stated at the beginning of the project that it was very unlikely to achieve results at the macro level, therefore the TAIS in Hungary did not aim at this level.

The meso level (most importantly civil society organisations) seemed to be adequate for piloting procedural improvements (new or improved services, methodologies) and better attitudes and/or knowledge of staff.

Concerning Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), it was stated that TAIS design cannot start until the group for which the action research is being carried out is consulted. A balance in terms of ethnicity, gender and local

communities was attempted. Ethical issues were also respected throughout the project: gender equality, informed consent, accessibility, respect for diversity, etc.

However, involvement of vulnerable individuals in the TAIS implementation was difficult because of the very nature of the TAIS: it targeted the social workers, not the refugee clients themselves. Improvement of the wellbeing of vulnerable refugees is expected not through the TAIS implementation in its direct form, but through the improvement of the social workers at NGOs that work with refugees.

Concerning the AR Strategy, innovative action research was expected to enable the TAIS participants to guarantee that the project would be flexible, and that it can be adapted to the changes in the needs expressed by participants. It happened in terms of adaptation to the change of the livelihood of many refugees and immigrants due to COVID-19 that affected economic sectors where a high share of foreigners was employed. It did not, however, change the overall integration policies or the outlines of refugee livelihoods in Hungary.

TAIS implementation should be inclusive, i.e. it should incorporate the opinions of the stakeholders and of the social group that participates in it; as well as accessible, i.e. all participants should access the planning and implementation process in all its phases.

SMART Criteria were observed, aiming at the implementation of an innovative TAIS that would be based on the following principles: specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, time-based. These criteria were important during the design as well as the implementation of the TAIS. Measurability of the impact would have been hard to achieve but the remaining criteria were met successfully.

Turkey

In AU point of view there were no difficulties and challenges in terms of the RAISD methodological approach. The Turkish target group were social workers who work with vulnerable and forcibly displaced people. The team aimed to organise trainings about how to work with vulnerable persons among forcibly displaced people, focusing on their rights- and needs-based expectations and their inclusion to the host community. The Turkish TAIS discovered problems of vulnerable forcibly displaced people and their relations with the host community regarding their daily life, work, language barriers, culture, education, health, decision making processes, etc. Applying socio-ecological models was beneficial in the context of the Turkish TAIS and contributed to enlightening the inter-relations between diverse levels.

According to the RAISD methodology, establishing an ARU was vital for the TAIS and an enlightening experience for the team. Anadolu University ARU members consisted of forcibly displaced persons themselves, non-governmental organisations, local administrators and decision makers, scientists, artists, students and social workers. This diversity in the design team of the TAIS, which was created to increase the capacity of social services personnel working with vulnerable groups, also enriched the AU team. In addition, thanks to the RRI dimensions, the implementation team had the opportunity to carry out an inclusive study. As said before, the TAIS target group was municipality social service. In accordance with socio-ecological modelling, the team had the chance to work in detail in micro, macro

and even meso levels, analysing the interrelations between these levels. As a result, RAISD turned into a great learning process and experience for all the participants.

Our very own ARU members also considered to use RAISD methodology in their own projects and works after took place in our project.

Jordan

NGOs like UNHCR, Care, Corps, to mention a few, refused to cooperate with the project team for unknown reasons. They also refused to sign MOUs and once sent representatives to unofficially attend the first meeting. The TAIS design was incorporated and adjusted to fit the Jordanian context. The team noticed some gaps between theory and practice especially when designing the trainings and during the evaluation process. One of the challenges presented because of the COVID-19 restrictions and the time pressure consequence. The team considers that if they had had much more time, the implementation, evaluation, analysis, and results would have been better.

Lebanon

The LIU Health committee worked to enrich all stakeholders with the coping tools needed to enhance them in developing their awareness and minimise the challenges in facing the Covid-19 pandemic emergency and consequent trauma situation. As per the discussions that took place during meetings, vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced have problems accessing basic health and education services.

Many refugees in Lebanon do not have access to free healthcare services, as they do not have a legal refugee status. In parallel with access to health services, the problem of accessing information mechanisms also arises. Especially COVID19 PCR testing became a stumbling issue to such groups, taking into account the cost.

According to the ARU and AB members, another important issue was access to education. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, an online committee regarding teaching was requested to be formed, and a site to online teaching was established in autumn 2021. In addition, those who had Internet access could get some guidelines with all the videos developed in Arabic as many FDP have language barriers.

LIU could have had a needs analysis conducted for better results. In order to answer these questions, the ARU team could have been asked to think 'outside the box' alternative approaches and to develop innovative solutions to complex problems the country and especially the FDP in Lebanon had faced and are still facing, the difficulties escalating day by day. It is necessary to think outside the conventional iron triangle of project management and to employ a long-term impact approach if we are to use similar approaches in the future.

6 Conclusions

The TAISs included in this deliverable offer examples of useful and tested pilot experiences for NGOs and other organisations working with FDP. The consortium hopes that the methodology explanation, and that especially the partner testimonies of the practical implementation, shared in the current document will help International actors when planning tailored strategies for FDP integration. The coordination team is fully aware of the complexity of using this novel research and innovation methodology and the triangulation of RRI, AR and SEMs, but the lesson learned is that an inclusive, flexible and collaborative research approach has proved itself fruitful and has given an active role to those actors that are normally left outside (especially FDP), when designing strategies that can contribute to improve their life conditions. For this reason, apart from explaining the positive aspects and benefits of the methodology approach and the TAIS implementation, the challenges and difficulties shared also contribute to the experiential learning process and give ideas about how to avoid the same mistakes in new social interventions. In getting feedback from the diverse stakeholders, the team has intended to be especially sensitive to the FDP voices and opinion of the most engaged TAIS implementers, trainers and collaborators.

Ethical issues are always a challenge for any research and innovation project and RAISD experiences with respect to these aspects can be helpful for future projects working in forced displacement and in the design of attention and inclusion strategy. It is too early to assess the medium and long-term effects of the TAISs, but in the short term, considerable impacts in the lives of the beneficiaries have been reported. For both types of beneficiaries, FDP and people who work with them, the TAIS generally contributed to enhanced capacities and professional skills, and in the case of the FDP, also to improved autonomy, fostering traits related to interpersonal relationships, self-confidence and gender awareness.

Partners' ideas about the usefulness and the possibility and feasibility of using this kind of strategies and methodological approaches in other projects can be an indicator of the success for the research and innovation approach. In general, many of the partners are already using the TAIS methodology or similar approaches in new project applications and new already granted project initiatives. And to our knowledge, many of the ARU members have seen these strategies very useful and inspiring for designing new social intervention programs for their organisations.

UCM is planning to use the methodology in future funding applications and also the team plans to continue working on new projects in which this methodology is adapted and revised. Other smaller initiatives are also being developed as a result of this experience, applied to education innovation projects with undergraduate and Master's degree students.

CESIE states that the overall methodological triangulation and the responsiveness in implementation of the strategy pilots have deeply impacted on their internal decision-making concerning target profiling and problem identification, hence on project planning priorities. This experience led to further discussion within the ARU on how the TAIS novelty selective-approach in education could be fostered and further developed within the vulnerable target groups. The AUCL knowledge and RRI perspective were integrated in two approved project applications under the AMIF program (Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund: PITCH and WINGS, 2022-2024).

The Helsinki University team considers that the key principles of the RAISD methodology need to be considered in any developmental and research project. They see the importance of participation of various stakeholders and particularly the beneficiaries and also, the aim of considering various societal levels. They consider using a similar methodology in new initiatives. One of the Helsinki team members is currently using the evaluation framework developed for the TAIS in a new research on evaluation the effectiveness of school-based youth work in Finland.

Menedék values the potential of the TAIS activities to facilitate access to diverse target works and thinks that to work with the ARUs, the constant iteration and feedback can be factors of success. As their work with the ARU has been evaluated positively by the implementation team, the team finds that for further projects and activities, the existing network of NGOs and service providers that implemented the TAIS or participated in the ARU's work should try to work together in order to apply the findings to their daily practices.

Anadolu University argues that since the methodology proved its efficiency, they plan to use the same methodology process in other projects that address the needs of refugees and local communities and deal with risk and crisis management, refugee entrepreneurship and empowerment and digital marketing.

The LIU team in Beirut plans to use the core methodological notions of RAISD in conjunction with a project called Internationalisation at Home. They also see the potential for its use in several Erasmus+ initiatives.

Yarmouk University team in Jordan has the same kinds of future use as the Turkish partners. They see the feasibility of the methodology in other projects that address the needs of refugees and local communities. YU team encouraged their ARU members to follow TAIS methodology in their up-coming projects and currently, there is one of this kind already running.

The project includes sustainability plans for the TAIS-related research methodology, especially in terms of continuing to research current attention and inclusion strategies of FDP and vulnerabilities related to diverse contexts. This is the core objective of the RAISD Observatory on Forced Migration, an international collaborative organism created among project partners and that has already started its activity in March 2021 and that will continue working after the project finishes, with the contributions of the consortium members and driven by a volunteer partner.

RAISD consortium, in the name of all the partner organisations would like to acknowledge the great contributions of the ARU members in all the participating countries, as well as the dedication of TAIS implementation team and course facilitators all over, and above all, our gratitude to the FDP who have placed their trust in our TAISs. We truly hope these experiences will contribute to improve their professional and personal development and alleviate their daily life conditions. Our warm thanks also goes to the NGOs and international aid organisations, experts, companies, journalists, social media writers, research assistants, researchers, students and administration representatives that have collaborated in the design, execution and evaluation of the TAISs

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Del. 3.4 TAIS methodology and guidelines [April, 2022]

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